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Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

Technical Report no. 253

EON 2000+ Earth Observation for Natura 2000+

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May 2004

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<p>TITLE EON 2000+ Earth Observation for Natura 2000+</p>	<p>REPORT IDENTIFICATION NERSC Technical Report no. 253</p>
<p>CLIENT European Commission</p>	<p>CONTRACT Contract No. EVG1-CT-2000-00028 EON2000+</p>
<p>CLIENT REFERENCE Michel Schouppe</p>	<p>AVAILABILITY Open</p>
<p>INVESTIGATORS from NERSC and NIERSC Stein Sandven and Victoria V. Miles with contributions from Sergey V. Maximov, Sergey Bartalev, Natalia Kalibernova, Gidske Andersen, Victor M. Pitulko</p>	<p>AUTHORISATION Bergen, May 2004 Ola M. Johannessen</p>
<p>OTHER PARTNERS Infoterra, UK; Highland Birchwoods, Scotland, UK; Environment Agency for England and Wales, UK; University of Joensuu, Finland; Finnish Environment Institute, Finland; GEOSPACE, Austria; Cemagref, France; Atelier Technique des Espaces Naturels (ATEN), France; GEOSYS, Spain; Asociacion para la Defensa de la Naturaleza, WWF/Adena, Spain; JRC/EIS (Inst. for Environment and Sustainability), Envip-Nat, Italy; University of Trier, Germany</p>	<p>ACKNOWLEDGMENT In addition to EON 2000+, the project work for the Norwegian and Russian case studies has been supported by the previous ARSGISIP project, ESA AO3-431 project "The study of Siberian boreal forests current state using ERS-2 data" and also by Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Centre in St. Petersburg, International Forest Institute in Moscow, Botanical Institute of Russian Academy of Science in St. Petersburg and Botanical Institute University of Bergen and Scientific Research Centre for Ecological Safety (SRCES) Russian Academy of Science.</p>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

EON2000+ is an RTD project co-funded by the European Commission, Research Directorate-General, Directorate D16, under contract number EVG1-CT-2000-00028. It builds upon the previous Framework IV project EON2000, which was finished in 1999 (please follow the link to download the Final Report of EON2000 at <http://geospace.co.at/EON2000.html>). EON2000+ has started on 01-June-2001. Project web site <http://www.eon2000plus.org>.

Changes in the global environment, such as those related to global warming, reduction in biodiversity, desertification and others have a direct impact on the European environment. Additional socio-economic and other pressures increasingly threaten rare landscapes, habitats and species throughout Europe. Individual Member States, the EU and Global Organizations have established a wide variety of legal mechanisms and international conventions for the protection of the environment and sustainable use of natural resources.

The contribution by this project to addressing the problem, of protecting the European environment, is the generation of information to assess; measure and monitor protected sites and associated landscapes using an indicator-based approach. These can then feedback to policy makers on the outcomes arising from the implementation of measures to protect the environment.

Many of these environmental impacts are trans-boundary and the economic activities that are the source of the impacts operates increasingly on a European level. This means that Europe-wide indicators are required to address the European dimension of the problem.

The aim of EON2000+ is to integrate environmental state and socio-economic pressure indicators for protection purposes in support of the conventions on Biodiversity and European biodiversity strategy.

The project focus on the development of generic indicators of the state of the environment (inventory and monitoring) & pressures (socio-economic), demonstrating multiple purpose indicators of a generic nature.

The method involves the integration and analysis of EO, environmental and socio-economic data in a GIS, calculation and testing of indicators and the dissemination to users and the general public via an Internet based system. This has involved working with end-users throughout the project lifecycle. Socio-economic and commercial exploitation issues will be addressed via the Business work package & plan, supported by a specialist subcontractor. EO data analysis includes assessment and use of new commercial VHR (Ikonos) satellite imagery. The project relates the results to relevant issues at the local end-user level to issues relevant to the EU policy level. Assess indicator harmonization on a pan-European level and the development of repeatable approaches on a variety of scales.

This project will enhance the quality of life of European citizens by contributing directly to the protection of European environment. This will have a direct benefit to citizens, where natural environments are sustained for the benefit and enjoyment of current and future generations.

The Indicators to be developed through the work of the project will complement additional indicators derived through other local, national and European initiatives. Together they will provide European Communities with independent information to gauge the local/regional outcomes and effects of policies implemented at National/EU level.

Conservation of the environment is an issue of concern to the majority of the European population voiced very clearly through various pressure groups and the citizen's political representatives. Environmental and pressure indicators will allow the public to better understand the current status of their landscapes, socio-economic activity and the complex relationship between the two. Relevant and easily comprehended indicators can also help convince the citizens that tools are available and actions are being taken to monitor and protect their environment.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Legislative Context

Changes in the global environment e.g. global warming, reduction in biodiversity, desertification and other changes have a direct impact on the European environment and often span the borders of European countries. Additional socio-economic and other pressures increasingly threaten rare landscapes, habitats and species throughout Europe.

The Habitats Directive is a European Community legislative instrument in the field of nature conservation that establishes a common framework for the conservation of wild flora and fauna and habitats of Community importance. Annex I of the Directive lists 198 European natural habitats, including 65 priority habitats i.e. habitat types in danger of disappearance and whose natural range mainly falls within the territory of the European Union. The Habitats Directive and the Wild Birds Directive provide for the creation of a network of special areas of conservation, called **Natura 2000**, to “maintain and restore, at favourable conservation status, natural habitats and species of wild fauna and flora of Community interest”. A Natura 2000 “Barometer” (<http://europa.eu.int/comm/environment/nature/natura.htm>) highlights the progress of Member States towards defining their Annex I lists of habitats and Natura 2000 network site selection.

There is also a recognised need to coordinate reporting obligations and develop monitoring standards across Member States, and to make that reporting more outcome-based (effectiveness). Issues of concern include the potential for appropriate environmental indicators and the relationships with other Directives.

1.2 Project Background

Earth Observation for Natura2000+ (EON2000+), is a Research and Demonstration Shared Cost Action project supported by the European Commission (DG Research) under the Fifth Framework Programme, within Energy, Environment and Sustainable Development. The project is a partnership of 14 members from seven European countries working for duration of three years (2001 – 2004) and follows on from a Fourth Framework project. Further details at: <http://www.geospace.co.at/EON2000p>

The aim of the ‘Earth Observation for Natura2000+’ project is to develop and demonstrate integrated indicators of environmental state and socio-economic pressures for environmental protection purposes in support of the conventions on Biodiversity and European Biodiversity Strategy.

The *focus* for the project is:

- The need and role of environmental indicators for environmental protection purposes (& conventions);
- EC Directives (‘Habitats & Species¹’ and ‘Wild Birds²’: Annex I Habitat Resources and ‘Water Framework³’: Protected Areas);
- The potential uses of spatial data sets (including Earth Observation (EO)).

This focus is reflected in the mix of project partners, with end users from environmental protection organisations (both government and non-government) and spatial data analysis experts (companies and research institutes), representing different local and national situations from six EU Member States and Norway (who also have project activities in Russia).

¹ Full title: ‘Council Directive 92/43/EEC on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora’.

² Full title: ‘Council Directive 79/409/EEC on the conservation of wild birds’.

³ Full title: ‘Council directive 2000/60/EC establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy’.

Name	Country	Profile /Activity	Website
Infoterra	UK	EO Service Company, (the 'EON Centre' and also in-country 'service provider')	http://www.infoterra-global.com/
Highland Birchwoods	Scotland	Environmental NGO (an in-country 'user')	http://www.highlandbirchwoods.co.uk/
Environment Agency	England & Wales	Government Agency (an in-country 'user')	http://www.environment-agency.gov.uk/
University of Joensuu	Finland	Research University (R&D and in-country 'service provider')	http://www.joensuu.fi/
Finnish Environment Institute	Finland	Government Agency (an in-country 'user')	http://www.vyh.fi/
Geospace	Austria	EO Service Company (an in-country 'service provider')	http://www.geospace.co.at/
CEMAGREF	France	Environmental Research Institute (an in-country 'service provider')	http://www.cemagref.fr/
ATEN	France	Nature Conservation Agency (an in-country 'user')	http://www.espaces-naturels.fr/aten/
GEOSYS	Spain	EO Service Company (an in-country 'service provider')	http://www.geosys.es/
WWF/Adena	Spain	Environmental NGO (an in-country 'user')	http://www.panda.org/europe/
Nansen Environmental Remote Sensing Centre	Norway	Research Institute (an in-country 'service provider')	http://www.nrsc.no/
University of Trier	Germany	EON R&D support: Indicators, plus in-country 'service provider')	http://www.uni-trier.de/
DG Joint Research Centre	EU	EON R&D support: Indicator & EO Research	http://www.jrc.it/
DG Research	EU	Policy & Administration	http://europa.eu.int/comm/research/

EON2000+ Project Partners

The EON2000+ project builds upon a previous Framework IV project EON2000 (completed in 1999), by extending to a wider range of habitats, biogeographic zones, countries and partners. It now comprises 14 members from 7 partner countries and is expected to complete in mid-2004.

Figure 1.1: Expansion to EON2000+ from the successful Framework IV project EON2000.

1.3 Project Challenges

EON2000+ cope with a broad range of diversity, in terms of:

- user requirements
- habitat type and geographic extent with respect to the broader countryside
- methodologies to address local user needs.
- Selected end users may not be fully representative of that country's user community, implying some uncertainty.

Indeed, we regard such diversity as a strength of the project.

Different countries are at different stages of implementing the Habitats and Species Directive, and differing degrees of readiness are apparent across regional users and the project requirements, as reflected in the Natura2000 Barometer.

The spatial extent of any area of interest will be important with respect to the feasibility and operational constraints, particularly in terms of data availability and spatial coverage. Natura 2000 sites may contain all or part of a habitat resource, and may vary in extent from one hectare to many thousands of hectares.

It is therefore desirable to be able to replicate the indicators beyond the geographic boundaries of the project test sites. EON2000+ will not follow a centralised algorithm philosophy, therefore a challenge will be to seek commonalities in analysis approach and across similar ecosystem types.

Different indicators are appropriate at different spatial analysis scales. EO data may be appropriate at some of these scales within a 'stratified' approach, depending upon the benefits of the imagery (e.g. resolution and wide area coverage) and how it may be integrated with other environmental and socio-economic data resources. However, it is entirely possible that EO may not be able to offer a strong role in some circumstances, through instrumental and thematic constraints, or through cloud cover problems.

Analysis techniques developed may not necessarily be applicable universally and the selection of habitats studied will relate to the particular project test sites and regional landscapes.

2 Work Programme. Norwegian and Russian Case studies

2.1 Involvement in the EON2000+ project

Focusing on boreal forest in Norway and the European part of Russia, NERSC contribute to the following work packages in EON2000+:

- * WP2 Indicator Development
- * WP3 User Specification Workshops
- * WP4 Demonstration
- * WP5 System Enhancement and Operation
- * WP6 Business and Socio-economic Analysis
- * WP7 Dissemination

A key feature is that EON2000+ has a very strong emphasis on local user requirements, addressed through an organisational structure defined by a service provider/end user relationship in each partnering country, linked through an EON 'Centre' and supported by R&D elements. The mix of project partners reflects this structure. This service paradigm is illustrated below:

WP2, WP3 and WP4 will be described in below chapters.

2.2 WP2: Indicator Development

2.2.1 Introduction

Indicators provide us with a synthetic representation of an environmental situation, by means of a value or parameter. They support work on reporting on the state of the environment, on measuring environmental performance and integrating environmental concerns in sector policies.

The approach in EON2000+ has been to:

- review a range of proposed (published) indicators intended for nature conservation, as a starting point for partners to illustrate an indicator concept to their users, drawing from such projects as ENVIP-NATURE,
- to learn more about similar indicator development programs in other countries and regions (e.g. North America), - to avoid re-inventing the wheel,
- to revise the initial published indicator selection in response to EON user requirements,
- to recognise and support local user needs, but also to understand and aggregate to cater for the European institutional perspective.

2.2.2 Main Characteristics of an Environmental Indicator

- it should provide a **representative picture** of environmental conditions, pressures on the environment or/and policy's responses;
- be **responsive to changes** in the environment and related human activities, be able to show **trends over time**, enabling a monitoring exercise;
- distributed over a broad geographical area, or otherwise **widely applicable**;
- be simple and **easy to interpret**;
- it should be theoretically **well founded** in technical and scientific terms;
- it should provide a basis for **European comparisons**;
- have a **threshold or reference value** against which to compare it so that users/policy makers are able to assess the significance of the values associated with it.
- it should lend itself to being **linked to economic models, forecasting and information systems**.

2.2.3 Existing initiatives elsewhere

The topic of environmental indicators has been under research for many years in many countries, though usually to cater for policy level. Most have been proposed in a top-down approach, where little has been provided on the working methodologies to actually apply them.

By contrast, a user-driven approach implies a diversity in requirement and a matching challenge in seeking common methodologies.

The more operational indicators tend to be those at national/European level, rather than at local user scale, suggesting local needs will require a more customised approach (rather than simply selecting an indicator from a list).

The basic concepts focus increasingly on the **OECD Pressure-State-Response** model. The advantage of this system and the reason for its success is its suitable framework for the verbalization of quality goals (in relation to state indicators) and action goals (in relation to pressure and response indicators).

2.2.4 Status of H&S Directive in Norway (& Russia)

Norway and Russia are both signatories of the Bern convention and as such also the obligations of establishing the Emerald network of ASCI. The involvement of project partners and end users from

these countries provides an opportunity to study common environmental issues and links to the Habitats Directive. And to relate these experiences to the commitment of both current EU member states and EU accession states.

2.2.4.1 Organisational reporting structure – organisations involved

Regionally and globally Norway's environmental cooperation is organised to either address common environmental problems or assist institutions with a broad mandate within or even beyond a given region. Norway is a member of the European Economic Area and cooperates on common environmental issues with the European Union.

The Ministry of the Environment has assigned the production of State of the Environment to the Environmental Authorities. The Norwegian Pollution Control Authority has the overall editorial responsibility. The state of the environment report is available at: <http://www.grida.no/soeno98/aboutsoe/aboutsoe.htm>

The Environmental agencies in Norway:

The Directorate for Nature Management (DN) is a national body that has the scientific responsibility for managing the Norwegian countryside. Its main tasks are to serve as the national implementing authority in the fields of biodiversity, land use planning and management, wildlife and freshwater resources and outdoor recreation. It is responsible to the Ministry of Environment on matters concerning nature management. The Directorate is also responsible for monitoring the state of wildlife and the natural environment, and for identifying, preventing and solving environmental problems. This work is intended to take place through co-operation with, and advice and information to, sectors of the population and other public authorities, both in Norway and other countries. The Directorate also has many tasks associated with regional and bilateral co-operation with other nations, in part through the Arctic Council for Environmental Conservation in the Northern Regions, the European Environment Agency (EEA), environmental co-operation with Russia, and as adviser to the Directorate for Development Co-operation (NORAD) regarding environment-related aid.

Norwegian Polar Institute Environmental Management and Mapping Department. The department has responsibilities regarding environmental management and counselling, environmental data collection and dissemination, and topographic and thematic mapping. The institute's mandate is:

- To be the strategic adviser of the central government regarding polar environmental issues to be responsible for the Ministry for the Environment's need for co-ordination of production, storage, and presentation of polar environmental data
- To administer environmental regulations for Norwegian territories and claims in Antarctica
- To be in charge of the topographic mapping of Svalbard, Jan Mayen, and the Norwegian territories and claims in Antarctica

The Norwegian Pollution Control Authority (SFT) is a directorate under the Ministry of the Environment. The main goal is to promote sustainable development.

SFT is working to ensure that pollution; hazardous substances and waste do not cause health problems, affect people's well being or harm nature's own powers of regeneration. In the area of environmental protection administration SFT have special responsibility for marine and freshwater pollution, chemicals which are hazardous to health and the environment, waste and recycling, climate changes, air pollution and noise as well as international environmental co-operation and support.

The tasks of SFT include:

- Monitoring and providing information about environmental development
- Providing the Norwegian Ministry of the Environment with advice, assessments and expert support
- Exercising authority through regulations and control measures

- Assessing the degree to which the different sectors of society have achieved their environmental goals
- Instructing and guiding county governors within the SFT's area of responsibility
- Promoting Norwegian objectives in international environmental co-operation
- Helping to improve the efficiency of the environmental protection work of developing countries
- Being prepared for and responding to acute pollution problems

A characteristic of today's environmental problems is that they require more integrated solutions. SFT is confronted with a number of national and global threats to the environment, which could have serious consequences in the long term. These are closely related to our high level of consumption, and far-reaching changes will be required to solve them. SFT recognises that the traditional tools of the environmental sector alone are not enough to achieve sustainable development. To help create such a development, we will put more emphasis on sustainable production and consumption and we will increase our efforts in the international arena. SFT is giving priority to work on climate change and the effects of energy consumption, chemicals which are harmful to health and the environment, and environmental problems in built-up areas, since these are some of the most serious threats to sustainable development.

Directorate for Cultural Heritage is responsible for the topic on "cultural heritage" and **Norwegian Mapping Authority** has provided most of the maps

2.2.4.2 Current status

Norway considers the Habitats directive an important process and a promising instrument and is prepared to continue its participation and contributions. On the national front Norway has increased its activity on Arctic environmental protection. The Euro-Arctic Barents Region was initiated and an Action Plan for the Environment was adopted recently. Norway is developing a strategy for environmental protection in the North and a White Paper on environmental protection in the Arctic archipelago of Svalberg which will be presented to Parliament. The aim is to produce new and advanced environmental standards, particularly in the area of habitat protection to ensure that environmental values of the area are taken care of. A report on new National Parks introduces thirteen new protected areas in northern Norway, including the marine environment and suggests expansion of six existing protected areas. An inventory for the protection of marine areas along the Norwegian coast has recently been conducted and similar work on an inventory of protection values of the marine areas in the Barents Sea and Svalberg continues. Following up the Biodiversity Convention, Norway is developing an Action Plan for biodiversity protection.

2.2.4.3 Implementation

The Norwegian Government appointed in April 2001 an expert group assigned to examine Norwegian legislation with the aim to strengthen legal measures for the protection of biodiversity in Norway, including how legislation responds to the issues within the scope of the Convention on Biological Diversity and other relevant international instruments.

Present legislation in Norway includes several laws for the protection of wildlife and the conservation of particular areas, but a more comprehensive legislation with the overall objective of protecting biodiversity as such has until now not been an issue. So far legislation has focused on protection of specifically targeted and threatened species or ecosystems and extraordinary or beautiful landscape. Approximately 8 % of the total area of Norway is today protected pursuant to the Nature Conservation Act, almost half of this being high altitude low productive mountain areas. Concrete plans exist that will increase areas of conservation to around 13 %. But even after this, the use of around 90 %, i.e. most of Norway, is in practice of decisive importance for whether one can prevent further losses of biological diversity. Furthermore areas at sea and marine species are inadequately covered by legislation.

Access to genetic resources and benefit sharing are identified as separate and priority issues as this is an area not yet subject to legislation in Norway. Likewise, the problem of introductions of alien species is another concern where the actual development trends in society such as increased global trade and mobility run ahead of the development of protective legislation.

A most pressing and challenging issue is the development of a more comprehensive approach to the protection of areas and habitats, both on land and at sea. Present legislation does not appropriately reflect the inter-dependency of conservation of species and habitats, or the close links between conservation of "man-made" biological diversity and cultural heritage. Liability issues, such as compensation for biodiversity loss, remain to be properly examined.

Although all land use in Norway is covered by the general provisions of the Planning and Building Act, few restrictions or mechanisms are in place for an effective and timely protection of a wider range of habitats, including habitats for threatened species. Once a wilderness country, true wilderness areas in Norway are today seriously threatened from a wide range of activities, and could be lost in less than one generation if due action is not taken.

2.2.4.4 National Indicator sets/projects

A proposal for the use of environmental indicators was laid out in late 1992. It defined an indicator as concerning "the state of, or the development of, important aspects concerning the environment." A well-developed set of indicators is able to provide an overall appraisal on the health of the environment. In developing its methodology, Norway relied on work done by the OECD (environmental Indicators: Basic Concepts"), as well as studies by the Economic Commission on Europe (ECE), Canada, Sweden and Denmark. Eventually, the use of indicators should allow mapping of long-term trends and international comparisons. Information on the environment may be difficult to evaluate in isolation. In answering questions such as: "How bad or good is the situation? Is it possible to do better?", etc, it is important to be able to compare the situation and development of various countries. Therefore, points of reference are needed.

Preferably, a set of indicators for Norway should be the same as or closely related to the sets of indicators used in other countries.

Norwegian project or project with Norwegian participation related to biodiversity, nature conservation and indicator development.

Refer to Annex C to find out more about people and organization in Norway related to biodiversity, nature conservation and indicator development.

LIVING FOREST (Norwegian project)

The project LIVING FORESTS Norway was initiated in 1995 to promote and contribute towards sustainable forest management in Norway. One of the most important project tasks is to prepare criteria, standards and documentation systems for sustainable forest management in Norway. To secure full participation and influence the work is done within a working group (DP2) where a wide selection of organisations is represented. In June 1996, the group unanimously adopted 6 preliminary criteria and about 160 preliminary indicators for sustainable forest management adapted to Norwegian conditions. Most indicators may be measurable by numbers with the objective to present a comprehensive description of Norwegian forest management. The next step is to carefully evaluate criteria and indicators and establish desired levels in order to arrive at standards for sustainable forest management. This work is in progress, and these standards will eventually form the basis of guidelines for the individual forest owner. The process of formulating standards is complicated. A special subgroup has been established to do this work. Forest owner associations, forest industries, environmental organisations, outdoor recreation organisations, consumer groups and the authorities are all represented in this group. The goal is for the work to be completed during 1997. The development of standards is partly based on trials and evaluation within 4 full-scale test areas with various Norwegian forest conditions. A separate consultant scientific committee is also participating in this work with an emphasis on the scientific aspects.

LIVING FORESTS has published a status report on the work regarding criteria and monitoring of sustainable forest management in Norway. This report is based on the preliminary criteria and indicators adopted in June 1996 by the working group (DP2).

The LIVING FORESTS working group DP2 has for the time being defined 6 main criteria and about 160 indicators related to sustainable forest management in Norway.

Criteria 2. Biological diversity. The forest must be managed so that the natural biological diversity of the forest landscape is maintained. The criterion includes diversity monitoring on the levels of the ecosystem, species and genus (Criterion 2 is described by 42 indicators).

BEAR – Indicators for forest biodiversity in Europe (Norwegian participation)

The project "Indicators for monitoring and evaluation of forest biodiversity in Europe BEAR", initiated in 1998, is a pan-European concerted action, bringing together expertise from 27 European research organisations to build a framework for the development of forest biodiversity indicators at various scales. The six major biogeographic regions of Europe are thus represented by partners from the following countries:

- Boreal region: Sweden, Finland, and Norway;
- Continental region: Germany, Hungary, Austria, Switzerland, and Italy;
- Atlantic region: U.K., Ireland, Belgium, France, Denmark, and the Netherlands;
- Alpine region: Switzerland, Austria, Italy, and Slovenia;
- Macaronesian region: Madeira, Portugal, Spain;
- Mediterranean region: Portugal, Spain, Greece, Italy, and France.

Partner 5. Norwegian Institute for Nature Research

Contact person: Bjorn Age Tommeras, Dr

Expertise: Dr. Science, in Zoology on interactions in bark beetle communities dynamics in forest. Leading research ecologist and responsible for NINA's forest research group and project leader for NINA's experimental fragmentation project in boreal forest. Follow-up the Convention on biological diversity, development of indicators and monitoring biodiversity, and use and conservation of biological resources. Program coordinator in the Norwegian Research Council for Conservation of biodiversity. NINA has competence on almost all-relevant taxa of invertebrates, cryptogames and vascular plants, birds and mammals.

Role: Coordinating the Boreal group of partners. Will contribute with Norwegian experience from research projects in forests distributed from inventory projects, monitoring of impacts from pollution, change in land use and forestry activities.

Environment and Climate Programme (Norwegian participation)

Centre for Earth Observation

Norwegian participation in WP 3100 Customer Requirements: Large scale environmental GIS applications in the Baltic Sea region: User requirements for land cover information derived from medium resolution satellite data BALANS

Planning and management in the Baltic Sea Region with land information from EO

http://balans.satellus.se/customer/publication/cust_req.pdf

Baltic 21 (Norwegian participation)

The Baltic 21 Forest Sector has decided to use the Pan-European criteria and indicators for sustainable forest management

Biodiversity indicators: Modelling the spatial distribution of aspects of biodiversity based on environmental parameters (Norwegian project)

The focus of the project is the evaluation of state and pressure indicators of biodiversity at 3 scales. Large scale biodiversity patterns (10 km²) will be analysed with respect to climate and topography. Medium scale patterns will be related to a wider range of environmental databases including climate,

geology, topography, soils and land use maps. At the landscape scale, indicator groups (bumblebees, butterflies, birds, plants) will be used to test whether landscape structure can predict local biodiversity patterns.

Correlative models will be used to relate internationally agreed aspects of biodiversity (based on species atlas data for plants, birds, amphibians, selected insects and mammals) with digital environmental data. Spatial modelling of biodiversity patterns will take place in a GIS environment. Multivariate techniques will be used to identify major determinants of biodiversity patterns at the medium scale. Quantitative landscape indices and detailed species inventories will be the basis for landscape-scale modelling (correlative and dynamic landscape models).

The results will provide a better knowledge-base for the selection of biodiversity indicators. The project will have applications in environmental monitoring, conservation planning and the assessment of the impact of land-use change.

Institution:

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2.2.4.5 National Indicator initiatives: Criteria and Indicators for Sustainable Forest Management in Norway

Norway has developed national indicators for sustainable forest management and forest biological diversity. This has been done through a national "Living Forests" project carried out in collaboration between the forest sector (including the forest industry), several NGOs, labour organisations and customer interests and the forest and environmental authorities. The national criteria and indicators are based on and fully compatible with the Lisbon resolution L2 of the Ministerial Conference on the Protection of Forests in Europe (under Criteria 4: Maintenance, Conservation and Appropriate Enhancement of Biological Diversity in Forest Ecosystems). In addition, several indicators that are essential in order to expose the situation / development in the Norwegian forest / forestry are added. Furthermore, in the process on selecting indicators, the possibilities of quantifying the indicators were emphasised. The indicators apply both at national and county level, if not otherwise specified. It should also be pointed out that the indicators will be used to construct time series to the extent this is possible. Presently, these national criteria and indicators are significant tools both for policy development, policy monitoring as well as reporting.

Table 1. Norwegian national list of indicators: Maintenance, conservation and appropriate enhancement of biological diversity in forest ecosystems

SCOPE	INDICATOR
Representative, rare and vulnerable forest ecosystems	Natural forest areas (cf. Helsinki 4.1 Changes in area of natural and ancient semi-natural forest types) Nationally protected forest areas (cf. Helsinki 4.1 Changes in area of strictly protected forest reserves) Forest areas subject to special management regulations (cf. Helsinki 4.1 Changes in area of forests protected by special management regime) Share of productive forest area where key biotope registrations have been made Size of area with key biotopes
Endangered species	Total number of forest species (cf. Helsinki 4.2 Changes in number and percentage of threatened species in relation to total number of forest species) Number of endangered species divided in categories (cf. Helsinki 4.2 Changes in number and percentage of threatened species in relation to

	total number of forest species)
Biological diversity in productive forest	<p>Extent of seed production plantations (cf. Helsinki 4.3 Changes in the proportions of stands managed for the conservation and utilisation of forest genetic resources)</p> <p>Extent of seed collection stands (cf. Helsinki 4.3 Changes in the proportions of stands managed for the conservation and utilisation of forest genetic resources)</p> <p>Share of mixed forest stands (cf. Helsinki 4.4 Changes in the proportion of mixed stands of 2-3 tree species (on productive forest land)</p> <p>Annual reforestation area (cf. Helsinki 4.5 In relation to total area regenerated, proportion of annual area of natural regeneration)</p> <p>Share of natural regeneration / planting (cf. Helsinki 4.5 In relation to total area regenerated, proportion of annual area of natural regeneration)</p> <p>Annual planted area of foreign species</p> <p>Share of broadleaf dominated forest</p> <p>Number of trees exceeding 30 and 45 cm in dbh</p> <p>Areas of cutting class V+30%</p> <p>Areas of cutting class V+50%</p> <p>Amount of dead trunks, divided on species, classes of break down and size classes at breast height (dbh)</p> <p>Bogs and wet-land areas divided on classes</p> <p>Annual area of new wetland drainage construction</p> <p>The share of productive forest area being dominated by spruce in afforestation regions</p> <p>The share of productive forest area being afforested by silvicultural activities in afforestation regions</p> <p>The shares of each vegetative class being afforested</p> <p>Non-economical operative forest areas</p> <p>The extent of important key biotopes (capercaillie, woodpecker species, marten and blueberry)</p> <p>Harvesting in the months of May and June</p>

2.2.4.6 Norwegian Ecological/Environmental Interests related to biodiversity conservation.

The protection of biological diversity is one of the most important global environmental challenges of our time. The challenge is linked to both preserving ecosystems and diversity of species and also to preserving genetic diversity. Two thirds of all species in Norway are related to the forests. The species require various living environments, and forest operations may affect the composition of species to a great extent. Some species require an environment that may be inharmonious to the trade utilisation of forest resources. This relates to species dependent on biological old forest and dead wood in particular.

Areas of Biological Importance - Key Biotopes

Natural forests are large virgin-like forest areas of special importance to biological diversity. The quality of the natural forest within the productive forest area must be maintained, primarily through the standards for forest area protection, key biotopes, harvesting methods, mountain forest, forest roads, bogs and wetland forest, old large trees and dead wood. Until these standards are revised, an evaluation will be made of the need for additional forest management regulations for these forest areas.

The registration of key biotopes will be implemented and their values will be documented and maintained. The economic responsibility of the forest owner is limited to 0.5 hectares on properties less than 50 hectares, and 1 per cent of the productive forest area on the larger properties. Until the results of ongoing research projects are made available, the forest owners may have key biotopes registered based on existing knowledge. Until the key biotopes are registered for a specific property, a cautious approach shall be taken and the values in likely key biotopes should be protected until competent professionals can make a registration.

Bogs and Wetland Forest

Normally, new establishment of drainage ditching on bog and forest wet land must be avoided. As an exception, drainage ditches may be constructed following a special registration documenting that the work is not affecting bogs and forest wet land that are rich or rare or that include special biodiversity values, special landscape values or have significance for recreational activities. Drainage maintenance and supplement ditching may take place if the need for restoring key biotopes is not present for this vegetation type on the property in question. As far as possible, in view of the stability and re-vegetation of the local species, closed-stand felling systems must be used in forest wet lands and in the bordering zones along dry forest land. Clear-cut harvesting must not be applied in bogs. Where natural conditions exist, through forest management and cutting systems, a multi-level forest stand must be maintained or developed in the bordering zones adjacent to bogs. Arrangements must be made to maintain the local species mix within the border zone.

Cultural Landscapes

Where natural conditions exist, stable edges of forest must be maintained and developed surrounding valuable cultural landscapes through forest management and cutting practises. Efforts must be made to maintain a local mix of species within these edges and, as far as possible; a considerable amount of hardwood should be included.

Distribution of Species

Arrangements must be made through forest management practices for utilising Norwegian species. In the established national forest regions, foreign species may only be used where problems exist in establishing a satisfactory reforestation using deciduous species and, to a lesser degree, in production of special quality products. The multiplying effect of foreign species must be controlled through forest management practices and by avoiding the use of species of high or uncertain spreading capacity. Where climatic and soil type conditions allow, hardwoods should feature prominently, through individual stands of hardwood, hardwood groups and as individual trees, including old, large hardwood trees. On individual property, a 10 per cent hardwood share must be the general rule. A mixture of spruce and fir should be preferred where conditions make this possible. Species that are rare in the local area must be safeguarded and/or encouraged through forest management measures.

Fertilising

The forest must be managed in such a way that nutritional leakage and nutritional loss is kept to a minimum. Areas of special environmental importance must not be fertilised. In order to increase forest growth, fertilising may be applied to suitable vegetation types such as lichen forest, heather-whortleberry forest, huckleberry forest and blueberry forest. Peat land may be fertilised where the re-vegetation has already been established. Vitality fertilising and lime application may be performed when it has been verified that forest vitality is impeded due to lack of nutrition or imbalance and the scientific verification of the positive effects of fertilisation has been made. During fertilising the forest, border zones along lakes and running water must be avoided in order to prevent run-offs. Fertilisation must not take place until the snow-melting phase is completed. In addition, the fertilising process must be adapted to prevailing weather conditions to minimise any nutrition leakage.

Forests Affected by Fire

Following forest fires exceeding 0.5 hectares in older forests, 0.5 hectares must be left untouched for a period of 10 years. For fires in older forests covering less than 0.5 hectares, the entire area must be left untouched for 10 years.

Forest Area Protection

Forestry measures that may adversely affect or destroy the resource base must not be applied, (see the Forestry Act decisions on forest protection). Redirected use of woodland for other purposes is permissible only after the authorities have made a total social evaluation of the Forest Roads Recreation and environmental values, in addition to general forest use and other commercial land use, must be duly considered during the forest road planning and construction stage. Road location and road standards must be planned in such a way that natural disturbances are minimised. The alignment must, as far as possible, be adapted to the landscape, and the road must be constructed without heavy cuts and fills. During the planning stage of new forest road construction, the forest owner must be able to document that the road location does not interfere with areas of registered particular

environmental values. New forest road construction in larger continuous forest areas with particular environmental and recreational values due to limited extent of technical interference should be avoided. This also applies to "Class 3" road construction in the permanent water protection areas of the community plan. In marginal forest areas where alternative use of the areas is of major importance, simple road solutions such as tractor roads and winter season roads should have priority.

Some reference:

European List of Criteria and Most Suitable Quantitative Indicators
<http://www.mmm.fi/english/forestry/policy/minkonf/criteria.htm#CRITERIA>

The Norwegian Society for Conservation of Nature, Oslo and Akershus (NOA)
SITUATION FOR THE OLD GROWTH FOREST
<http://www.noa.no/Saker/Skogbruk/Oldgrowth/english/old%20growth.htm>
<http://www.noa.no/Saker/Skogbruk/Oldgrowth/english/Front.htm#info>

2.2.4.7 Russia – Organisation reporting structure.

Russia joined the Convention on Biological Diversity in February 1995, thus continuing existing activities in biodiversity conservation and sustainable use. In full understanding of a cross-sectoral and changeable character of the issue of compliance with obligations under the Convention, on July 1, 1995, the Russian Federation Government issued a special resolution to establish the **Cross-Sectoral Commission for Biological Diversity Conservation**. Among other activities the country participates in the Clearing House Mechanism on Biodiversity (CHM) and established the Russian National CHM Focal Point (The **Russian Conservation Monitoring Center** of the GEF Project "Biodiversity Conservation in the Russian Federation"). The Centre is responsible for the information support for the biodiversity conservation.

2.2.4.8 Russia – Current status

Convention on Wetlands of International Importance Especially as Waterfowl Habitat (Ramsar convention). The USSR joined the Convention in 1975, since then only three wetlands with the Ramsar status remained in Russia. The Government Act of 1994 expanded the List of wetlands of international importance up to 35 located in 21 Russian Federation regions.

Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Fauna and Flora (CITES). Russia (USSR) has been a Party of the Convention since 1976. A draft project of the Rules for Import and Export of CITES Specimens is now prepared. A joint-action plan for federal authorities to enhance control over preying, trade and customs clearing of CITES specimens was elaborated. Similar plans exist in many RF subjects.

In order to develop raising international cooperation in biodiversity conservation, it seems important that Russia joined both the Bern Convention and the Bonn Convention. Bern Convention adoption is required by the country membership in the European Council and participation in the Pan-European Landscape and Biological Diversity Strategy. At present Russia is involved only in the Memorandum on Mutual Understanding Concerning Measures on the Conservation of the Crane (*Grus leucogeranus*).

Cooperation with international NGOs in biodiversity conservation is no less important. The country is involved in joint efforts with NGOs such as, World Conservation Union (IUCN), World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF), and such NGOs as International Wetlands Organization, TRAFFIC, and Tiger Trust. They are assisting Russia in the running of biodiversity conservation projects, especially in European Russian forests, wetland inventory, protection of *Bison bonasus*, *Panthera tigris* etc.

Program for the Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF) is one of the four programs within the Arctic Region Environmental Protection Strategy ratified by Canada, Denmark, Greenland, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Russia, Sweden and the United States of America. CAFF plans include species and habitats conservation and application of traditional knowledge. The country works on the research aimed at establishment of a circumpolar network of protected areas and flora conservation. The

program allows to achieve high efficiency of research efforts, information exchange, environmental management and rational use of Arctic resources.

2.2.4.9 Russia – National Indicator sets/projects

The activity on the assessment of environmental protection activity in the Russian Federation, using the “pressure-state-response” model is now conducted by a joint group of the experts from the OECD and Russia. This has included the development of environmental indicators for the Russian Federation and its regions following the approach and recommendations of OECD and has promoted the generation of geo-referenced data. This data includes various kinds of impacts (emissions to atmospheric air, discharges to inland waters, formation of toxic wastes), status of separate environment components (air, inland and underground waters, land resources, biodiversity conservation). This has also led to recommendations for priority funding of various directions of environmental protection activity and perfection of state statistic systems in the field of environment.

The presented set of indicators is not complete according to OECD methodology. The set of indicators is designed on the base of the state statistical reporting base and Goscomecologiya of Russia for 1996. The insufficiency of the initial information for previous years has meant that it is not possible to analyse complete indicator dynamics during the previous 10-15 years, and further research is required for a true selective thematic retrospective analysis.

2.2.4.10 Norwegian-Russian co-operation in environmental protection

Events affecting the environment in neighbouring countries may also affect the state of the environment in Norway - in the negative sense due to trans-boundary pollution and more positively in connection with co-ordinated management of joint animal populations and areas of natural environment. The protection of a region's biodiversity and common cultural heritage often requires effective bilateral cooperation. Nordic cooperation is a key channel for exerting an influence on EU decisions and for resolving issues in the Nordic region and the neighbouring area. Other priorities include cooperation to address environmental issues in the Arctic, nature conservation, protection of heritage sites, and integration of environmental concerns in other sectors, such as fisheries and industry. The Nordic countries work together to strengthen environmental legislation and management in Eastern Europe, and promote investment in environmental measures in Eastern European countries. Through the Barents cooperation and environmental partnership with Russia we are focusing on the development and reinforcement of Russian stewardship as well as cooperation on specific measures. Development and strengthening of Russian expertise is necessary in all sectors, and it is vital that Norwegian-Russian cooperation programmes in areas such as fisheries, environmental protection, industry and energy policy all take place within a framework of sound resource management and sustainable development.

2.2.4.11 Russia and EU

Russia has actively joined international activities in the field of the nature conservation. On 16 November 2000 Russia and the European Commission made an **“Agreement on cooperation in science and technology between the European Community and the Government of the Russian Federation”** (<http://fp5.csrs.ru/Russian/Involvement/EURussiaSTagreement.pdf>).

The main purpose of the agreement is that the Parties shall encourage, develop and facilitate cooperative activities in fields of common interest where they are pursuing research and development activities in science and technology.

Cooperation with third countries and international organizations in Community RTD is explicitly mentioned in the EC Treaty as one of the activities to be promoted when pursuing the objectives of Community research policy. It is also mentioned as one of the instruments for implementing the Framework Programme, in which it is now, as the "second activity" of FP5, fully integrated.

Russia, although outside of the EU is actively supporting EU initiatives in the field of biological diversity and conservation at the national and international level e.g. in relationship to Natura2000 and support by LIFE and INCO-Copernicus programmes.

2.3 WP3: User Requirements

The detailed user requirements have been collated from a tree round of project workshops, questionnaires or direct user discussion, held in EON2000+ countries.

A review of the status of the implementation of the Habitats Directive in each country, from workshop discussions, reflected the differences between Member States and their background legal, political and social/cultural situations with regards to implementing conservation measures.

The main specific requirements of the Habitats Directive are grouped under two headings, the first is entitled 'Conservation of natural habitats and habitats of species' and comprises Articles 3 to 11 inclusive. The second is entitled 'Protection of species' and comprises Articles 12 to 16 inclusive. Annex I of the Directive lists 198 European natural habitats, including 65 priority habitats i.e. habitat types in danger of disappearance and whose natural range mainly falls within the territory of the European Union. The Habitats Directive and the Wild Birds Directive provide for the creation of a network of special areas of conservation, called **Natura 2000**, to "maintain and restore, at favourable conservation status, natural habitats and species of wild fauna and flora of Community interest".

A Natura 2000 "Barometer" (<http://europa.eu.int/comm/environment/nature/natura.htm>) highlights the progress of Member States towards defining their Annex 1 lists of habitats and Natura 2000 network site selection.

The situation with regards current issues surrounding the implementation of the Habitats Directive is discussed in the main User Requirements Document (Project deliverable D8, a summary of which available on the web site <http://www.eon2000plus.org>). In particular in light of the recognition, within the Sixth Environmental Action Plan (6EAP), of a need for more effective 'streamlined' data collection and monitoring, and collection of data with more relevance to undertake causal links to policies (i.e. assessing the effectiveness of legislation). Environmental indicators have been discussed in this context with a focus on spatial information (and the role of EO and GIS), and the future role in EU policies. Indicators developed should be based on a biogeographical approach, which requires them to be identified at a local level, yet providing comparable information.

2.3.1 Users

NERSC has established contact with users in Norway: Norwegian Nature Research Institute, and in Russia: International Forest Institute in Moscow, Centre of Ecological Safety Russian Academy of Science in St. Petersburg.

Norwegian Institute for Nature Research NINA is a national and international centre of expertise within applied ecology. Their expertise is applied in research, monitoring and assessments. The areas of activity are natural diversity, Nature in the north, Land use and landscape, Climate, Use of nature and so on. NINA conducts research on the basis for the conservation and sustainable use of species, ecosystems and landscape. With its long tradition of research, its wide knowledge of nature and with the help of the most recent methods NINA undertakes projects to assist all with responsibility for management of the natural environment. <http://www.ninaniku.no/>

The International Forest Institute (IFI), Moscow, Russia

International Forest Institute as the international non-government organisation. Institute is under the status of Russian Academy of Natural Sciences. The activity of International Institute aimed at the development of international co-operation in fields of ecology, conservation, reproduction and rational use of forest. The main directions of the Institute scientific activity are: inventory and monitoring of forests at the base of space observation techniques and geo-information technologies; use and reproduction of forest resources; conservation of forests from fires, pests and diseases; organisation of especially protected natural territories. <http://www.ifi.rssi.ru/>

The Scientific Research Centre for Ecological Safety (SRCES) Russian Academy of Science (RAS) implements co-ordination of activities on interdisciplinary basic research in the field of ecological safety. <http://www.srces.spb.org/>

User interaction has been carried out using questionnaires and direct dialogue with users by telephone and in person. The plans to hold a user workshop were not carried out, having taken into account that our users are located in different countries and different parts of country (Norway). The demonstration material with detailed description of data and techniques used has been sent to the users. We developed a special 4-part questionnaire (see Annex B) to feel out our user requirements for indicators and data, cost benefit and feasibility of current techniques for incorporating and processing EO data. Questionnaires were sent out to the users.

The main points of discussion were to elucidate the degree to which the demonstration indicator data and techniques satisfy user requirements.

2.3.2 Requirements

User requirements are connected with such themes as: state of habitat (habitat mapping); change in state of habitat (habitat monitoring); status of habitat/species (vulnerability). The main categories of indicators types required are: descriptive indicators of state, descriptive indicators of the status of vulnerability and changes in that status, descriptive indicators of condition of quality and changes in that status

In neither Norway nor Russia is remote sensing is a widespread approach for environmental monitoring. However, users confirm that satellite remote sensing data could create a set of tools to assist in sustainable forest management activity and biodiversity conservation. The maps based on remote sensing data provide a basis for making improved estimates of habitat state and changes in its state, as well as providing tools for operational monitoring.

State of Habitats

Use – management

Theme – state

Type – descriptive, indicators

Spatial scale – site/habitat level

Temporal level – short medium term

The purpose is to provide a survey and mapping of the area that are important for biological diversity and to classify their value. The specific aim is to get information of location, characteristic and quality of forest habitats. The information is required to provide information for forest protection and conservation purpose. Thematic mapping is used as a basis to take a management decision. The condition of vegetation will be used as an indicator of habitat state. The requirements for mapping and monitoring terrestrial vegetation and forest ecosystems in particular have recently led to important remote sensing development such as the combined use of a wide range of satellite sensors. The aim is to integrate different sensor data in order to obtain more information than can be derived from each of the sensors individually.

The satellite data will be analysed in order to assess their ability to detect and separate different vegetation features, thereby developing sufficient knowledge to define representative signatures for each studied forest parameter. A number of areas of interest within the test areas will be extracted for each studied class. Assessment of spectral behaviour of each class and class separability will use statistical techniques. Assessment will be done in two respects: to large features, i.e., forest and non-forest (including grassland and wetland), and more precisely to forests, i.e., forest type (e.g. broadleaf and coniferous), age, density and height. The final step is classification and thematic fusion. For different data, the different classification procedures will apply, for example, unsupervised single data clustering and supervised class labelling for optical data, and supervised classification by thresholding SAR backscatter.

Thematic forest cover digital maps will be produced by the most appropriate sensor data identified during the study. The results will be validated at each stage by establishing correlation between retrieved and in-situ data and visual comparison. The most appropriate methods of accuracy assessment will be determined in the research. Based on the thematic fusion by progressive, iterative integration of each classified data layer, the synthetic map of the area will be produced. The satellite-derived forest map will be compared with existing Russian and Norwegian forestry maps. The validation analysis of the discrepancies will be performed by cross-tabulation procedures and visual comparison.

Change in habitat state

Use – management

Theme – state/pressure

Type - descriptive indicators

Spatial scale – site/habitat level

Temporal level – short medium term

Data – high-medium resolution

The monitoring is intended to provide information on changes in species distribution, abundance, etc., and in habitat and ecosystem over time, and the cause of such change. Satellite-derived thematic forest maps will serve as the basis for a change detection analysis. The particular change detection approach includes the post-classification comparison and image difference methods. This will quantify the changes of the forest habitats in the region. Here, transformation such as forest-non-forest or non-forest-forest (including changes after forest fires and clear-cutting) and also change of forest parameters e.g., coniferous-broadleaf-mixed.

2.3.3 Requirement Characteristics:

- The Use (or purpose) of the requirements is primarily for management and reporting from a practical point of view (e.g. monitoring of agricultural measures, surface water level in Wetlands, pastoralism pressures in mountainous regions...). The scale at which this management and planning is required needs to be further explored in developing the requirements. This should relate to the approach of indicators as: a) specific policy instruments and initiatives and b) Headline Indicators.
- Spatial scale characteristics are at a regional and / or habitat scale. The habitat extent is within a biogeographic region encompassing the complete habitat resource (and any specific sites with that habitat). A regional spatial scale of analysis requires a broader description of information but exactly what level of detail / information is required must be further assessed to develop an appropriate and feasible indicator.

The spatial extent for the analysis will be important to the feasibility and operational constraints, particularly in terms of data availability and spatial coverage. Natura 2000 sites may contain all or part of a habitat resource and may vary in extent from one hectare to many thousands of hectares and there is an important requirement to address habitats across the wider countryside. Habitats within EON2000+ test sites are still quite difficult to identify spatially. Their evolution both in terms of extent and quality is again a challenge, in particular for indicator definition.

The geographic reporting unit may be varied (e.g. catchment to EU NUTS level) and a certain flexibility in reporting is required.

- Temporal characteristics are much less well defined at this point but those that have been commented on reflect the reporting requirements of the Habitats Directive, every six years, or a need for annual information.

2.3.4 Addressing the Feasibility

Current 'off the shelf' indicator constructs may be relevant to specific requirements and will be reviewed in due course. It is not the aim of the project to research new techniques but to utilise current methodologies with a sound scientific background and demonstrate the results.

The role of Earth Observation data within the context of developing indicator products has been discussed in the URD and the various factors with regards to its appropriate use.

The business case for the project will address the *costs and benefits* of proposed indicators, in terms of

- the need for the information (that is not otherwise available);
- existing methods (providing more efficient techniques)
- how existing information is complemented (providing a missing context).

A measure of project success will be the degree of uptake of indicator products by the end user organisation and the involvement of such organisations in the demonstration and dissemination.

Requirements by user:

IFI

1. State of Habitats (forest mapping)
2. Change in state of Habitat (forest change detection)

SRCES

3. State of Habitats (forest mapping)
4. State of Habitats (forest state assessment)

NINA

5. State of Habitats (forest mapping)
6. Change in state of Habitat (land use/cover changes)

Why are the data identified in the 'user requirements' needed?

Requirement 1,3,4,5:

The requirements are to provide a survey and mapping of the areas that are important for biological diversity and to classify their value. The specific aim is to get information of location, characteristic and quality of forest habitats. The information is required to provide information for forest protection and conservation purpose. Thematic mapping is used as a basis to take a management decision. The condition of vegetation will be used as an indicator of habitat state.

Requirement 2,6:

The requirements are to provide information on changes in species distribution, abundance, etc., and in habitat and ecosystem over time, and the cause of such change.

What are the immediate responsibilities and obligations of the organisation that the user requirements will satisfy?

Requirement 1-6:

Reporting and practical use for management at local and national level

General driving forces of acquiring the information:

Russian National biodiversity strategy and Action Plan (Ministry of Natural Resources, National biodiversity strategy and Action Plan. Moscow, Russia, 2001.

Russian Federation Forest Code, RF Federal Act No. 22-FZ. Adopted By the State Duma On January 22, 1997

Forestry and forest protection act (1993). (The objective of the Act is to promote forest production, forest protection and afforestation) (<http://english.dirnat.no>)

The Planning and Construction Act, The Nature Protection Act and the Outdoor Recreation Act (all have an effect on the management of the forests in Norway) (<http://english.dirnat.no/>)

Nature Conservation Act (1970) (provisions for conservation of forests) (<http://english.dirnat.no/>)

Living forests Standarts for Sustainable Forest Management in Norway (<http://www.levendeskog.no>)

The use of EO data alone or in combination with other data, to satisfy user requirements.**(1) The potential for EO data to satisfy user requirements that are not met by other existing data**

The envisioned benefit from using EO data for the users are possibilities to continuous acquisition of data; broad regional coverage; good spatial resolution; map-accurate data; possibility of stereo viewing; large archive of historical data.

(2) The potential for EO data to combine with or replace other existing data in satisfying user requirements

Requirement 1, 3 and 4

Combined use of satellite SAR and multi-spectral data, along with an extensive in situ data set of ground measurement. To evaluate the potentials of use multitemporal and multi-spectral sensor observation to trace the dynamic of changes in forest ecosystems.

(3) The cost of using EO data compared to the cost of other existing data

The cost of using EO data is different for the users. For Norwegian user (NINA) the ground/field observation is still most cost effective data and they consider the EO only as worthwhile additional information.

For Russian users (IFI, SRCES) the satellite remote sensing is useful if not essential for spatially detailed mapping and monitoring due to the vastness of the forest areas and their inaccessibility for regular field measurements. But it is still quite expensive for non-profit organisation to use EO data and especially in operation mode and the ground-based forest observation still provides the fundamental information and EO data are used as additional information source.

(4) The attitude and knowledge of users on the use of EO data. Other factors hindering use of EO data.

All users have a good expertise and experience to use of EO data and to map and monitor forest ecosystem by remote sensing and GIS technologies. But still users consider the EO data mostly as a mapping and monitoring tools for biodiversity conservation purpose and not as tool to get new information about biodiversity.

2.4 WP4: Demonstration of Indicator Products to Users

2.4.1 Project Test sites

The habitats and European biogeographic zones of the studied project test sites, by country, are listed in Table 1. These sites and habitats have been selected through the workshops and involvement of end user partners.

Table 1: Test sites and habitats

Country	<i>BIOGEOGRAPHIC ZONE</i>	Habitat(s)	Test Site(s)
UK – England UK – Scotland	Atlantic	Wetland Woodland	Catchment (2) (FP4 site tbc)
Finland	Boreal	Grassland Mires / Forest	Somero (SW Finland) Patvinsuo (E Finland)
Austria	Alpine	Forest / Grassland	Kalkhochalpen Bluntauental Sieb. Gerlosplatte
Germany	Continental	Woodland / Grassland, (Bogs, Heaths)	Hoher Flaeming (NE Germany)
France	Mediterranean Alpine	Wetland Grassland / Forest	Camargue (S France) Mercantour (W Alps France)
Spain	Mediterranean	Wetland	Doñana (S Spain) (SCIs: n° ES0000024, and, ES6150008)
Norway Russia	Atlantic/Boreal Boreal	Forestry Forestry	Flisa Kurgal Peninsula (NW Russia) Egorievsk forest (Moscow)

Fig.1. NERSC test sites locations

2.4.2 Test sites and data

Demonstration studies will be carried out for three different test sites located in south-eastern Norway and in the north western Russia in the St. Petersburg and the Moscow regions. The specification of the test site location was determined through the user. Test sites different one from another by geographical location, ecological conditions and types of pressure caused of stress, by protection status, habitats and biodiversity. A brief description of each test site is given below.

For each studied area, a special database including EO and in-situ data has been developed. The spatial- and temporal resolution required in the northern boreal area is presumably less then in central European areas. This is due to the fact that the boreal area is sparsely inhabited, is less prone to change and has large ecological units. The spatial resolution of Landsat MSS (79 m) and Landsat TM images (30 m) is adequate for habitat mapping and monitoring. Remote sensing with VIR sensors is, however, adversely affected by cloud cover, haze and illumination conditions, especially problematic in the high latitudes. In contrast, Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data can be used regardless of weather or illumination, assuming relatively flat terrain, and can be useful for thematic mapping and monitoring of the forest habitat. SAR data from European Remote Sensing Satellite (ERS) 25 m resolution and Japanese Earth Resources Satellite (JERS) 24 m resolution will be used in our demonstration.

The data bank contains various forest information and maps on three test sites. It consists of digital topomaps (1:25 000 – 1:100 000), maps of forest stand limits and a number of additional maps presenting spatial distribution of the degree of forest damage caused by clear cutting, insects activity and industrial pollution. The attributive component of the data bank consists of the taxational characteristic plantation data including species-age structure and biometric information.

All of the data are spatially corrected and (where possible) updated to fit in spatial and temporal domains of satellite data planned for analysis in the framework of the current project.

2.4.2.1 Test site “Flisa”(Norway)

Fig.2. Location of “Flisa” test site

The Flisa area is in Østerdalen, central-eastern Norway and is a part of the Glomma River system, which is the largest in Norway.

The relief is characterised by gentle valley with forests. This is south boreal zone dominated by coniferous species, i.e. *Picea abies*, *Pinus sylvestris*. Main forest types are mixed coniferous dominated by pine and mixed coniferous dominated by spruce and mixed forest dominated by deciduous. Land use of the area is in transformation especially in the form of urbanisation. These changes have significant impact on the habitat and cause such problem as habitat fragmentation.

Based on the temporal and spatial resolution of the required analyses, the following EO and in-situ data were collected. Landsat-5 TM: July 1999; Landsat MSS: June 1976, May 1979, Sept. and Oct. 1985; ERS SAR 1995 and 1999; topographic digital maps 1: 250000 1:100000 1:50000; geologic digital maps; vegetation and forestry maps 1:100000 1:25000; field observation data and DEMe

2.4.2.2 Test site "Kurgalsky Peninsula"

The Kurgalsky Peninsula is located in the north-western part of Russian near the Estonian border (58:43:00N 29:25:00E). The Ramsar test site is a regional wildlife refuge ('Zakaznik'). It is located in the taiga zone (south taiga sub-zone).

Fig.3. Location of "Kurgalsky peninsula" test site

The habitats of the area include patches of broad-leaved and mixed forests, coastal meadows and marshes with alder and oak⁴, Sphagnum fens, floodplains, dry meadows, and reed-beds. The site exhibits a high species diversity of flora and fauna, supporting numerous species of regionally or globally threatened plants, mammals, birds, amphibians and reptiles.

The wetland supports large migrating and breeding populations of numerous species of waterfowl. The region is subjected to a variety of anthropogenic impacts main of them are atmospheric and water pollution which cause serious damage to local habitats.

The test site database include EO data: ERS1/2 SAR, JERS SAR, MSU-SK RESURS -01, Landsat MSS and in-situ data: topographic maps; cartographic data of forest; data on forest damage; forest taxation data and geo-botanical descriptions and results of ground survey.

2.4.2.3 Test site “Egorievsk”

The Moscow region test site is situated in the Egorievsk forestry (90 km southeast from Moscow) and covers 8950 hectares. The main habitat types of the territory are stands of coniferous and deciduous species, with pine, birch, spruce and also aspen, black alder, oak and lime being the predominant ones. Dating from the last forest husbandry (1998-99) a number of changes caused by fires and forest cutting (clear cutting, sanitary cutting, advance thinning etc.) took place in forestry and cause on forest fragmentation.

Fig.4 Location of “Egorievsk” test site

⁴ Natura 2000 network: reference list of habitat types and species
[\[http://europa.eu.int/comm/environment/nature/natura.htm\]](http://europa.eu.int/comm/environment/nature/natura.htm)

The test site database include EO data: ERS1/2 SAR, JERS SAR, MSU-SK RESURS -01, Landsat MSS and in-situ data: topographic maps; cartographic data of forest; data on forest damage; forest taxation data.

2.4.3 Demonstration and indicator products.

2.4.3.1 Indicator Demonstration Broad Forest Habitat Inventory: Distribution, Area and proportion in a site

Requirement: forest distribution and its changes

Description of indicator: This indicator shows the total area of the territory under forest and forest land, including treeless areas within forests, clear cut areas, areas with thinly scattered forests and burnt forest areas.

Demonstration material: Forest mapping (test site Kurgalsky peninsula (see Annex C-1) and Flisa test site (see Annex C-2))

Assessment / comments and discussion: Indicator collects and reports information on status and trends of forested ecosystems. The specific aim of the indicator use is to get information of location and characteristic of forest. The indicator is used as a basis to take a management decision. The indicator is interesting for the users that it could be used as a basis for the other indicators (example 3.2;3.3;3.4;3.5). Indicator presents in form of forest maps derived from remote sensing data. The demonstration shows good results of using remote-sensing data (Landsat and Landsat-SAR combination) to identify forested and non-forest areas. ERS SAR data bring more accuracy to eliminate wetlands that would be difficult using optical data alone.

Users mentioned that higher classification accuracy needed to achieve practically significant gains in efficiency. User also mentioned needs in new land cover classifications every 5 years, or updates every 5 years through change detection.

Users conclude that remote sensing creates the opportunity to use relatively inexpensive and regularly acquired land cover data as an alternative to aerial photography. Creating a forest/non-forest mask from satellite imagery may offer a cost-effective alternative to interpretation of aerial photography.

2.4.3.2 Indicator Demonstration Broad forest Habitat state: trend in forest conversion to other land uses; land cover change mapping

Requirement: changes in habitat and ecosystem over time, and the cause of such change

Description of indicator: This indicator quantifies the changes of the forested area and forest habitats

Demonstration material: Change in land-use (Flisa test site (see Annex C-3))

Assessment / comments and discussion: The indicator is intended to provide information on changes in forest habitat and ecosystem over time, and the cause of such change. Satellite-derived thematic forest maps serve as the basis for a change detection analysis. The change detection approach used in demonstration includes the post-classification comparison and image difference methods.

The indicator demonstration shows that satellite imagery makes possible to reliably identify the non-forested areas and quantify the changes of the forest in the region. The demonstration shows to the users the % of forestland transformation especially in form of urbanization. There are several ways to quantify the results of land use change. Users remark that the way used in demonstration is one of the most straightforward to tabulate the totals for each land use cover type and view the trends between the years.

The approach causes a user discussion. They mentioned that despite the demand for environment and natural resources information, many existing maps and digital databases do not meet user requirements. One of the main causes, though underestimated, is the type of classification or legend used to describe basic information such as land cover. Classifications and legends are generally not comparable with one another and, very often, are single-project oriented. Despite the fact that there exist many classification systems throughout the world, there is no single, internationally accepted, land-cover classification system. The users concerned that approach used in demonstration is good, but single-project oriented and could not be used in operational way.

2.4.3.3 Indicator Demonstration Broad Forest Habitat Inventory: Share of broadleaf/coniferous in a site

Requirement: changes in habitat and ecosystem over time, and the cause of such change

Description of indicator: The indicator reports the area of a variety of forest types. Forest types described by dominant species of trees. Reduction of dominant species (stock reduction) testifies to destruction of ecosystem and habitat state and habitat loss.

Demonstration material: Forest type mapping (Kurgalsky peninsula test site (see Annex C-4), Egorievsk (see Annex C-5) and Flisa test sites (see Annex C-6))

Assessment / comments and discussion: User confirm they growing need for comparable, reliable and up to data information on forest type. However, mapped forest information is quite limited. Satellite Earth observation offer synoptic and repetitive data. User mentioned that a number of forest type classification change detection techniques have been developed. However, the diversity of forest and the variety of these techniques have lead to differing results.

During the discussion of updating the data in this indicator, it was decided that a more objective method will needed to determine whether a forest type had increased, decreased, or remained the same over a period of time. At the moment a simple comparison was used between the first and last time points (i.e., 1985 and 1999) to make a decision about trend. A new method should be implemented whereby a trend line will fit to the time series for a given forest type. Only those data series that had a significantly positive or negative trend line were reported as such for this data update.

By regularly examining it may be possible to detect deleterious changes and modify management strategy to reverse the changes.

2.4.3.4 Indicator Demonstration Broad Forest Habitat state: area and proportion of coniferous species damaged by air pollution

Requirement: information of forest condition and degree of anthropogenic pressure

Description of indicator: Main coniferous species are especially sensitive to air pollution. Degree of crown defoliation in the stands is an indicator that characterizes the forest condition

Demonstration material: Forest state mapping (Kurgalsky peninsula test site (see Annex C-7))

Assessment / comments and discussion: The development of the degenerative process in pine needles leads to a decrease of the rate of respiration and photosynthesis, slowing down the rate of chlorophyll synthesis. This is reflected in the tree's external indicators, resulting in colour change and death of pine needles – this change can be imaged from, for example, Landsat MSS.

It is apparent from the demonstration that the degree of forest degradation has strong dependencies with optical remote sensing data. But users insist that the ground truth data is still closer to the truth than the NDVI map. Nevertheless, optical data have the potential for identifying areas of damaged forest, at least where some in situ data are available for validation. The correlation between ground-truth and remote sensing data is encouraging.

2.4.3.5 Indicator Demonstration Broad Forest Habitat state: forest under threat due to air pollution effect

Requirement: information of forest condition and degree of anthropogenic pressure

Description of indicator: The degree and spatial distribution of ecological anomalies in forests that appear under the influence of air pollution

Demonstration material: Forest state mapping (Kurgalsky peninsula test site (see Annex C-8))

Assessment / comments and discussion: The end user is quite satisfied with demonstration material and presented results. Since 1992, the Scientific Ecological Center in St. Petersburg has conducted a monitoring study of the forests in St. Petersburg Region and it was quite interesting for them to see the correlation between in situ data characterizing the degree of forest damage and remote sensing data. It is apparent from the correlation analysis that a range of parameters defining the degree of forest degradation has strong dependencies with optical remote sensing data. It was discussed and the

demonstration showed the degree and spatial distribution of ecological anomalies in north-western Russian boreal forests that appear under the influence of air pollution can be effectively investigated and revealed using a combination of remotely-sensed data from different satellite sensor systems (radar and optical, low and high resolution) and a thorough ground truth data set from the monitoring at grid points.

The user concludes that the results of the study and multi-sensor approach in general can be useful applied for similar purposes in different areas.

3 Discussion

a) Meeting the requirements OR where the 'gaps' are

The demonstration meets the user requirements to provide a survey and mapping of the areas that are important for biological diversity and to classify their value and the requirements are to provide information on changes in species distribution, abundance, etc., and in habitat and ecosystem over time, and the cause of such change.

The specific aim is to get information of location, characteristics and quality of forest habitats. The information is required to provide information for forest protection and conservation purpose. Thematic mapping is used as a basis to take a management decision. The condition of vegetation is used as an indicator of habitat state.

b) If EO data may be used to either supplement current data, or provide new data otherwise not available

The remote sensing-derived land and forest type classification maps provide substantially greater spatial detail than the contour maps based on ground-truth data. In itself, this illustrates an advantage of using remote sensing data; however, the accuracy of the classification of forest types is still not high.

c) Include overview of Benefits assessment of work/demonstrations – how EO/data may improve current situation.

The envisioned benefit from using EO data for the users are possibilities to continuous acquisition of data; broad regional coverage; good spatial resolution; map-accurate data; possibility of stereo viewing; large archive of historical data.

For user demonstrate the possibility of combined use of satellite SAR and multi-spectral data, along with an extensive *in situ* data set of ground measurement. Also the potential to use multi-temporal and multi-spectral sensor observations to trace the dynamic of changes in forest ecosystems was evaluated.

4 Conclusion

NERSC has established contact with users in Norway: Norwegian Nature Research Institute, Directorate of Nature of the Norwegian Ministry of Environment and Norwegian Space Agency, and in Russia: International Forest Institute in Moscow, Centre of Ecological Safety Russian Academy of Science in St. Petersburg and Botanical Institute in St. Petersburg.

User interaction has been carried out using questionnaires and direct dialogue with users by telephone and in person. The plans to hold a user workshop were not carried out, having taken into account that our users are located in different countries and different parts of country (Norway).

The demonstration meets the user requirements to provide a survey and mapping of the areas that are important for biological diversity and to classify their value and the requirements to provide information on changes in species distribution, in habitat and ecosystem over time, and the cause of such change.

In neither Norway nor Russia is remote sensing is a widespread approach for environmental monitoring. However, the demonstrations show that satellite remote sensing data could create a set of tools to assist in sustainable forest management activity and biodiversity conservation. The maps based on remote sensing data provide a basis for making improved estimates of habitat state and changes in its state, as well as providing tools for operational monitoring.

The remote sensing-derived land and forest type classification maps provide substantially greater spatial detail than the contour maps based on ground-truth data. In itself, this illustrates an advantage of using remote sensing data. High resolution optical data have the potential for identifying areas of damaged forests, at least where some *in situ* data are available for validation. We conclude that the demonstration show the capability to use combined remotely sensed data to identify the degree of forest degradation under air pollution impacts. However, identification of the density and composition of atmospheric deposition is still possible only using ground measurements

The results and approached shown in demonstration can be useful applied for similar purposes in different areas.

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Annex A: Questionnaire

Requirements for indicators of environmental state and pressure indicators – forest biodiversity conservation

The aim is to establish the 'user-driven' selection, definition and assessment of requirements, leading to the development and demonstration of appropriate environmental indicators.

Please answer the following questions. Thank you.

1. Name of your organisation? (max. 160 characters)

2. What is the kind of your organisation?

- Administrative
- Scientific
- Industrial
- Social

3. What is the main activity of your organisation?

- Nature/resource management
- Nature/resource conservation/protection
- Nature/resource exploitation
- Different /please, specify

4. Do you use any specific environmental indicators in your work?

- Frequently
- From time to time
- No

Part A: INDICATORS

5. Why is the information on environmental indicators required?

- Policies, management improvements
- Monitoring, inventory improvement
- Pressure / impact assessment
- Nature, biodiversity conservation
- Increase awareness, which should lead to changes in behaviour
- Provide information to others
- Simplify your own activity
- Any other reason – please, specify

6. What will it be used for?

- Management
- Specific policy instrument
- Research (scientific purpose)

7. Requirement themes:

- Habitat/species mapping
- Change in state (inventory)
- Status of a habitat/species (vulnerability)

- Landscape – landscape structure and land cover / use
- Biodiversity modelling
- Pressures (socio-economic) indicators
- Other – please, specify

8. Categories of indicator types required:

- Descriptive indicators of state
- Descriptive indicators of area (extent) and changes in that extent
- Descriptive indicators of the status of vulnerability (to pressures) (and changes in that status)
- Descriptive indicators of condition of quality (and changes in that status)
- Welfare/policy effectiveness indicators of the outcomes of implementing the policies and pressures

9. Spatial scale of indicators:

- Site level – criteria and indicators for site state (inc. protected area and special conservation area)
- Habitat level – criteria and indicators per habitat type (forest, grassland, peat bogs..)
- Species level – criteria and indicators for specific species

10. Temporal scale: How sensitive should be indicators to changes over time?

- Indicators measurable in the **short-term** because changes are significant/observed over a short-time period and data are available to compute them
- Indicators which require additional work and data collection efforts and which are therefore only measurable in the **medium term**
- Indicators measurable only in the **long term** because they would need significant data development work.

11. What spatial levels of analysis (monitoring, management) are required?

- Regional
- Landscape
- Habitat
- Species
- Multiple levels

Part B: Data

12. What kind of data is mostly used in your work?

- Geographical databases
- Aerial photos
- High resolution satellite remote sensing data
- Low resolution satellite remote sensing data
- Other data /please, specify

13. What are the main data sources for your work?

- Local, site-specific data
- National data
- European or other international data

14. What kind of data is more useful for your work?

- Ground/field observation data
- Earth observation/remote-sensing data

15 What are your requirements for data:

Accuracy : (% accuracy)

- High
 Satisfactory

Precision (How well does it need to be measured to be useful?)

- High
 Satisfactory

Frequency (How often?)

- Monthly
 Every year

Timeliness (at what time of year, season)?

- Winter
 Spring
 Autumn
 Summer

16. Do you have any other specific requirements? (max. 160 characters)

Please, specify

17. Can your data requirements be met using EO data?

- Yes
 No

18. What spatial and spectral resolution are required?

- High resolution
 Medium resolution
 Low resolution

Part C: Costs

19. Where do you the envision benefits from using EO data?

- Continuous acquisition of data
 Regular revisit capabilities (resulting in up-to-date information)
 Broad regional coverage
 Good spectral resolution (including infra-red bands)
 Good spatial resolution
 Ability to manipulate/enhance digital data
 Ability to combine satellite digital data with other digital data
 Cost effective data
 Map-accurate data
 Possibility of stereo viewing
 Large archive of historical data

20. What are the data & operational costs associated with the indicator?

- Data acquisition
 Data processing
 Data interpretation
 Data analysing
 Qualified personnel
 Equipment
 Software

21. Which data are most cost effective for your purposes?

- Ground/field observation data
- Aerial photo data
- Satellite data: high resolution, middle resolution, low resolution
- Other specific data

22. Can EO data provide your organisation a cost-effective source of information (either directly or through modelling inputs) that could not otherwise be met?

- Yes
- Partly/only as a worthwhile additional information
- No

Part D: Techniques**23. What is your opinion about the feasibility of current techniques for incorporating and processing EO data?**

- Good enough
- Difficult to use – should be simplified
- Not well developed
- Needs special software/equipment/personnel

24. Are these recognised, established techniques (rather than new research)?

- Yes
- No

25. Are they scientifically sound and repeatable?

- Yes
- No

26. Are you satisfied with the errors (and level of acceptance) in the processing and end result?

- Yes
- No

27. Which EO data processing / analysis techniques can meet the requirements?

- Change detection
- Classification
- Data combination
- GIS
- Others

Annex B: People and organisations in Norway

Organisation	Address	Name of the project or activity	Key Person(s)	Contact information
The Royal Norwegian Ministry of the Environment	Postboks 8013 Dep. N-0030 Oslo, Norway http://odin.dep.no/md/ http://193.217.72.200/	Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) National Report on Implementation of the Convention on Biological Diversity	Tone Solhaug, Senior Adviser	Ph: + 47 22 24 59 54 Fax: + 47 22 24 27 56 tone.solhaug@md.dep.no
Directorate for Nature Management	N-7485 Trondheim, Norway Tlf.+47 73 58 05 00, Fax. +47 73 58 05 01 postmottak@dirnat.no http://www.dirnat.no	CBD-CHM (Clean House Mechanism) Focal Point in Norway:		
Svanhovd Environmental Centre	N-9925 Svanvik Phone +47 78 97 36 00 Fax: +47 78 97 36 01 svanhovd@svanhovd.no http://www.svanhovd.no/	The Joint Russian-Norwegian Work Group on Biodiversity http://www.svanhovd.no/jubile_bros/bio.html	Øvre Pasvik nasjonalparksenter	
Norwegian Crop Research Institute		<i>Management and restoration of the agricultural landscape</i>		http://www.planteforsk.no/prosjekt/dok/AN2405.htm
Taiga Rescue Network	http://www.taigarescue.org	The Last of the Last The Old -Growth Forest in Boreal Europe		http://www.taiga-rescue.org/old-growth/last.shtml
Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (NINA)	Tungasletta 2, N-7485 Trondheim, Norway http://www.ninaniku.no	BEAR Indicator for forest Biodiversity in Europe http://www.algonet.se/~bear	Dr Scient Bjørn Åge Tømmerås Research Director, Division of Conservation Biology <i>Regional co-ordinator: Boreal group</i>	bjorn.a.tommeras@ninatrd.ninaniku.no Tungasletta 2, N-7485 Trondheim, Norway Tel +47 73 80 15 52 Fax +47 73 80 14 01

The Norwegian Forest Owner's Federation	http://www.skog.no/	Living forest Standart for sustainable Forest Mangment in Norway http://www.levendeskog.no	Nils Bøhn	Tlf. kontor: 22 01 05 71 Tlf. priv.: 66 82 02 77 Mobil: 905 44 565 e-post: nils.boehn@skog.no
The Norwegian Forestry Association		Living forest	Mr Erling Bergsaker	
The Norwegian Pulp and Paper Association		Living forest	Mr Kjell Myhrer	
The Norwegian Sawmill Industries' Association:		Living forest	Rolf Hatlinghus	
The State-owned Land and Forest Company:	http://www.statskog.no/	Living forest	Mr Torkell Vindegg	
The Norwegian United Federation of Trade Unions:		Living forest	Mr Kjell Martinsen	
The Norwegian Ministry of Agriculture:		Living forest	Mr Steinar Bø	
The Norwegian Ministry of Environment		Living forest	Mr Knut Simenstad	
The Norwegian Society for the Conservation of Nature:	http://www.naturvern.no/	Living forest	Mr Thor Midteng	
WWF Norway	http://wwf.no	Living forest	Mr Arnodd Håpnes	
The Norway National Council for Outdoor Recreation:		Living forest	Mr Øystein Dahle	
The Association of Intermunicipal Outdoor Recreation Boards:		Living forest	Mr Morten Dåsnes	
The Norwegian Consumer Council		Living forest		
Environmental Labelling in Norway		Living forest	Ms Hilde Jervan	
Norwegian forest society	http://www.skoginfo.no	Living forest		

GRID-Arendal	http://www.grida.no /	The Nordic set of environmental indicators, prepared for the Nordic Environmental Monitoring and Data Group, is primarily based on the OECD Core set.	Åke Bjørke Project manager	brown@grida.no +47 370357 65
Norwegian Institute of Land Inventory (NIJOS)		OECD	Ms. Wendy FJELLSTAD	P.O. Box 115 N-1431 Ås Tel.: (47 64) 94 97 04 Fax.: (47 64) 94 97 86 Email: wef@nijos.no
Norwegian Crop Research Institute Division Landvik		OECD	Mr Aasmund ASDAL	N-4886 Grimstad Tel: (47) 37 25 77 00 Fax: (47) 37 25 77 10 email: aasmund.asdal@planteforsk.no
Ministry of Environment, International Division	P.O.Box 8013 Dep. N-0032 OSLO	Baltic 21	Mr Stein Paul Rosenberg	Phone: +47 22 24 60 24 Fax: +47 22 24 27 55 E-Mail: sro@md.dep.no
Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry Department	P.O. Box 8007 Dep., N-0030 OSLO	Baltic 21	Ms Berit Hauger Lindstad	Phone: +47 22 24 93 75 Fax: +47 22 24 27 54 E-Mail: berit.lindstad@ld.dep.no
GRID-Arendal		Baltic 21 Forest sector goal and core indicator		http://www.grida.no/nordic.html

Annex C-1: Indicator Demonstration Broad Forest Habitat Inventory: Distribution, Area and proportion in a site (Test site “Kurgalsky Peninsula”)

Indicator

Definition

This indicator shows the total area of the territory under forest and forest land, including treeless areas within forests, clear cut areas, areas with thinly scattered forests and burnt forest areas.

Geographical scope

Local, regional

Information needs /Questions that this indicator must answer

forest distribution and its change. Decreasing % of forested area will lead to habitat destruction and habitat loss. Forest area and forest type are foundational for most of the indicators

Indicator purpose

Reporting and practical use for management at local and national level

Project User Requirement state of habitat. Basic indicator will provide information for forest management. Indicator will identify key landscape features and areas important for the conservation of biodiversity.

Policy Relevance

Regional and National relevance to forest sustainable management

National biodiversity strategy and Action Plan (Ministry of Natural Resources, National biodiversity strategy and Action Plan. Moscow, Russia, 2001.

Russian Federation Forest Code, RF Federal Act No. 22-FZ. Adopted By The State Duma On January 22, 1997

Relevance to Habitat Directive

Site and issue of concern (conservation objectives/pressures) relevant to the indicator
regional wildlife refuge, variety of anthropogenic impacts

Habitats/Species of European Interest relevant to the indicator

1630 Boreal Baltic Coastal meadows

7310 mires

9020 natural old broad-leaved deciduous forest (Quercus)

Relevance to International Indicator framework

- OECD Category -State
- Structure/Function
- EEA core set indicator: Forestry, State
- MCPFE, Bear, ... CRITERION 1: Quantitative indicators: 1.1.

Intellectual source of the indicator

(2001) Indicators and Environmental Impact Assessment: Designing national-level monitoring and indicator programs. UNEP/CBD/SBSTTA/7/12 – Montreal, Subsidiary Body on Scientific, Technical and Technological Advice

Environmental Indicators. Committee of environment protection of St Petersburg and Leningrad region (http://www.ecolog.nw.ru/LE_2.HTM)

Approach

Wetlands and other similar areas are expressed better in radar images than in visible-band images, primarily due to the high sensitivity of microwave backscatter to variations in soil moisture and the presence or absence of surface water. The variations in grey tones in a SAR image provide a basis for discriminating different surface types by means of visual interpretation. Here, for the purpose of locating and outlining wetlands, a composite of two ERS-1 SAR images with the spatial resolution reduced to 100 m was used. A straightforward, expert-supervised classification of this composite was carried out to identify wetland and non-wetland classes. As a result such composite from different seasons is conducive to an image-map of wetland distribution. One can readily identify the wetlands, bogs and similar terrain types. Landsat MSS images were classified using maximum likelihood supervised classification. Furthermore, the ERS-1 SAR composite was combined with classified Landsat MSS imagery to assess location of general land-cover classes. Four general classes were separated: forest, wetlands, agricultural field, and water bodies.

Fig. 1 Multi-sensor approach for forest mapping

Demonstration

To assess the distribution of forests, an allocation of general land use classes was carried out using the Landsat MSS and ERS-1 SAR composite. The forested areas allocation is shown at the maps in Figure 2, where 2a represents the in situ data and 2b - the results of satellite data analysis. A comparison of these two maps shows that agriculture fields, urban areas and water-body classes are well identified from the satellite data classification. Although there are some dissimilarities in the boundaries and locations of small fields on these maps, this can be accounted for by the difference in resolution between the in situ and remote sensing-derived maps. The in situ map has a 1:200 000 scale, whereas the remote sensing map has resolution about 100m. As regards the forest and wetland

classes, there is some discrepancy between them; nevertheless, the discrepancy is relatively minor and the delineation of the wetlands is reasonably good.

Fig.2 The allocation of major types of land use classes derived from Landsat/MSS and ERS/SAR composite (left). The map (right) representing forested area.

Annex C-2: Indicator Demonstration Broad Forest Habitat Inventory: Distribution, Area and proportion in a site (Test site “Flisa”)

Indicator

Definition

This indicator shows the total area of the territory under forest and forest land, including treeless areas within forests, clear cut areas, areas with thinly scattered forests and burnt forest areas

Geographical scope

Local, regional

Information needs /Questions that this indicator must answer

forest distribution and its change. Decreasing % of forested area will lead to habitat destruction and habitat loss. Forest area and forest type are foundational for most of the indicators

Indicator purpose

Reporting and practical use for management at local and national level

Project User Requirement:

state of habitat. Basic indicator will provide information for forest management. Indicator will identify key landscape features and areas important for the conservation of biodiversity.

Regional and National relevance to forest sustainable management

Forestry and forest protection act (1993). (The objective of the Act is to promote forest production, forest protection and afforestation) (<http://english.dirnat.no/>)

The Planning and Construction Act, The Nature Protection Act and the Outdoor Recreation Act (all have an effect on the management of the forests in Norway) (<http://english.dirnat.no/>)

Nature Conservation Act (1970) (provisions for conservation of forests) (<http://english.dirnat.no/>)

Living forests Standards for Sustainable Forest Management in Norway
(<http://www.levendeskog.no>)

Relevance to Habitat Directive

9010 * Western Taïga (anemone hepatica, conitum septentrionale)

Relevance to International Indicator framework

- *OECD Category*- State
- Structure/Function
- *EEA core set* indicator: Forestry, State
- *MCPFE, Bear, ...* CRITERION 1: Quantitative indicators: 1.1.

Intellectual source of the indicator

(2001) Indicators and Environmental Impact Assessment: Designing national-level monitoring and indicator programs. UNEP/CBD/SBSTTA/7/12 – Montreal, Subsidiary Body on Scientific, Technical and Technological Advice

Living forests Standards for Sustainable Forest Management in Norway (<http://www.levendeskog.no>)

Approach

The **Flisa** area is within the Norwegian southern-boreal and mid-boreal zone. Both zones are primarily dominated by coniferous species, *i.e.* *Picea abies*, spruce, and *Pinus sylvestris*, pine, however, there are also large areas of wetland, bogs and mires. A supervised forest type classification was produced from the 1999 TM image. All images are haze corrected, ortho-rectified and topographically normalized in front of the classification. Signatures are derived from a combination of ground truth data, interpretation of unsupervised classification of historical data in conjunction with ground truth data, interpretation of aerial photos, and knowledge acquired during the field campaigns about the landscape and about vegetation in the test area. In addition local key informants has been involved.

In the end user resolution four different raster maps are generated, differing in methods for post-classification and filtering prior to resampling. Supervised forest type classification was also produced for remote sensing data from 1985, 1979, and 1976.

Two different algorithms are used in conjunction with the resampling. The first algorithm is using a majority filter based on a 3 by 3 neighborhood. The second algorithm applies a majority filter in most cases but in neighbourhoods (3 by 3) dominated by forest classes three additional classes are generated: 1. mixed coniferous dominated by pine; 2. mixed coniferous dominated by spruce and 3. mixed forest dominated by deciduous.

Subsequent resampling to end user resolution is of nearest neighbourhood type in both cases.

These datasets, respectively referred to as the 'majority data' and the 'mixed data', are further processed in order to recode cloudy/hazy pixels and, in conjunction with them, an overrepresentation of urban pixels. Urban areas in the catchments are small and few; hence large clusters of urban pixels are misclassifications. Several different classes with hazy characteristics were generated in the classification. These classes and the urban class are extracted and the files are clumped, *i.e.* neighbouring pixels of similar classes are clustered. All urban pixels are subsequently eliminated; *i.e.* 'eliminate' is a process that replaces all pixels below a size threshold with the majority class in a 3 by 3 neighbourhood. The output is a raster map where small clusters of urban pixels are recoded to null. This output is then used as a mask in which all nulls are replaced by the original image and non-nulls, *i.e.* clouds, are recoded. Areas to be recoded are either substituted by the 1985 land-cover classification or by forest and/or bog classes, according to which type of haze class that is recoded. The forest class chosen is either pine for the majority data or 'mixed coniferous forest dominated by pine' for the mixed dataset.

Fig.1 Methodological processing steps

Demonstration

The following classes are used in the classification:

- **deciduous forest**,
- **pine forest**: one class is pine growing on soils dominated by lichen rich vegetation, labelled pine1. This type is found on dry moraines. The second class is pine growing on richer soils dominated by different berries and heather, e.g. *Vaccinium spp.*, *Empetrum spp.* And *Calluna vulgaris*, labelled pine2;
- **spruce forest**;
- **young forest**: These classes are mainly defined from or in conjunction with aerial photos. One class is young forest labeled as **young coniferous**, another is **mixed young forest** and a third class is **young deciduous**.

Fig. 2 The forest map retrieved from satellite data.

- **clearcuts:** areas that are clearcut in 1999. These are defined from the TM image;
- **bogs:** in general bogs in this area are peat bogs and vegetation growing on peat. They can be classified according to different criteria, e.g. way of creation, hydrology, morphology, vegetation etc. In the catchment the trophic character is either ombrotrophic (nutrients only from rainwater) or minerotrophic (nutrients also from water that has been in contact with mineral soils). In Hedmark there are both types and some bogs are used for peat extractions while some are protected areas. In the current classification scheme these strict definition criteria are not focused, rather it is only distinguished between the wetter parts of the bog where few or no trees can grow (labeled non-forested bogs) and the drier parts where some forest occur (forested bogs). In addition there is one class for drained bogs.

Furthermore the four classes sand/soil, water, agriculture, and clouds/haze were classified.

The second algorithm applies a majority filter in most cases but in neighbourhoods (3 by 3) dominated by forest classes three additional classes are generated:

1. **Mixed coniferous dominated by pine**
2. **Mixed coniferous dominated by spruce and**
3. **Mixed forest dominated by deciduous.**

Supervised classifications of the 1976, 1979 and 1985 MSS data are made in several steps. The same reference data as used for the 1999 classification are used in classification of MSS data. However, classes subject to changes, e.g. clearcut and young forest, are revised for each dataset. Nevertheless, the lower resolution of MSS data makes it difficult to distinguish classes that are easier to distinguish in the TM image: e.g. non-forested bogs and clearcuts, and young forest and forested bogs. Because the main use of MSS images is for a time-series analysis where the output should be age of forest stands, a forest mask is made from the TM image and a new set of raster maps where only these areas of the MSS images are classified are produced.

Accuracy assessment was made for the landuse classification, and an **overall accuracy of 79%** was obtained based on a total of 254 points distributed among 10 classes. Classes of young forest are assessed as one class. Individual user's accuracy ranges between 0.35 (settlements) to 1, individual producer's accuracy ranges between 0.63 (open/wet bog) and 1. After accuracy assessment post-classification and resampling to end user accuracy is done and totally four products are generated.

Annex C-3: Indicator Demonstration Broad forest Habitat state: trend in forest conversion to other land uses; land cover change mapping (Test site “Flisa”)

Definition

This indicator quantify the changes of the forested area and forest habitats

Geographical scope

Local, regional

Information needs /Questions that this indicator must answer

To provide information on changes in habitat and ecosystem over time, and the cause of such change.

Indicator purpose

Reporting and practical use for management at local level

Project User Requirement

change in state of habitat/habitat fragmentation. Land use transformation in form of urbanisation/ impact of these changes on forest habitats

Regional and National relevance to forest sustainable management

Forestry and forest protection act (1993). (The objective of the Act is to promote forest production, forest protection and afforestation) (<http://english.dirnat.no/>)

The Planning and Construction Act, The Nature Protection Act and the Outdoor Recreation Act (all have an effect on the management of the forests in Norway) (<http://english.dirnat.no/>)

Nature Conservation Act (1970) (provisions for conservation of forests) (<http://english.dirnat.no/>)

Living forests Standarts for Sustainable Forest Management in Norway (<http://www.levendeskog.no>)

Relevance to Habitat Directive

Land use transformation/ habitat fragmentation

9010 * Western Taiga (anemone hepatica, conitum septen-trionale)

Relevance to International Indicator framework

- Identify OECD -State

-Structure/Function

- Identify criteria/indicator from the EEA core set indicator: Forestry, State

- MCPFE, Bear, ... CRITERION 1: Quantitative indicators: 1.1.

Intellectual source of the indicator

(1998) Annex 1 of the Resolution L2: Pan-European Criteria and Indicators for Sustainable Forest Management. Third Ministerial Conference on the Protection of Forests in Europe – Lisbon, Ministerial Conference on the Protection of Forests in Europe.

Living forests Standarts for Sustainable Forest Management in Norway (<http://www.levendeskog.no>)

Approach

An unsupervised classification of Landsat MSS and TM 1985/1999 scenes has been performed for the Glomma (Flisa) areas. The rectification of the Landsat MSS scenes is based on digital and conventional maps in addition to rectification points from field. During processing of the Landsat TM image, we used 4 bands corresponding with Landsat MSS. Based on our and other researchers' experience we found out that the results do not much depend on the difference in resolution. So, we worked with original resolution of both images.

Classifications with 16, 40 and 80 classes were identified to characterise the land cover. The interpretation of the classified images was primary based on ground-truth data from fieldwork. The interpretation and classification of the images is a process continuously revised by the ground truth data from fieldwork.

The selection of training sites is based so far on the unsupervised classification of the Landsat MSS scenes with 16 classes as well as on fieldwork in the Glomma study area. All these classes have been checked; however they still need revisions and collection on in situ data particularly in agricultural and human made areas.

The 16 classes of land cover in the unsupervised classification of Landsat MSS scenes for the Flisa areas represents water, water mixed with stone/grass (bridges, shores of lakes), pine, spruce, mixed forest, deciduous forest, marsh, human made area, different classes of cultivation land (shifting cultivation, pastures, grass), snow, and clouds.

The change detection approach includes the "post-classification comparison" and "image difference" methods.

Fig. 1 Multi-temporal remote sensing data for land use change detection

The urban and residential area is usually confused with water area and bare farmland. So in order to improve classification result, we must modify classification map by using some thematic maps. Comparing the classification map with some thematic maps identifies the pixels that are different between these maps. Then, we modify the pixels in the classification map. In order to briefly describe the way it works, we take the water, for example. In the water thematic map, a pixel belongs to water. If the pixel also belongs to water in the classification map by the possibility relaxation classifier we consider the classification result of the pixel is right; if the pixel doesn't belong to water, we consider the classification result of the pixel is wrong, and should modify the classification result. In the modification process, we can modify the classification result into a right classification result under the experts' knowledge and can also classify the pixel again by the maximum-likelihood classifier, if the possibility value belonging to a certain class except water is maximum, the pixel belongs to the class.

Demonstration

Land use of the area is in transformation especially in the form of urbanisation. These changes have significant impact on the habitat and cause such problem as habitat fragmentation. At the diagrams is shown the land use changes occur in ten years time between 1989 and 1999. The diagram show incising areas of open mires (on 30%), mires edge with some vegetation (on 25%), agricultural land (on 10%), agricultural land not in use (on 15%) and urban areas (on 13%). Some decreasing can be seen in drained mire/peat extraction (on 20%) and recent clear-cut areas (on 6%).

- | | |
|---------------------------------|------------------------------------|
| 1. open mires | 2. mires edge with some vegetation |
| 3. drained mire/peat extraction | 4. agricultural land |
| 5. agricultural land not in use | 6. urban areas |
| 7. recent clear cut | |

Fig.2 Diagram shows the land use changes (difference between 1989 and 1999)

The level of accuracy is encouraging – the overall accuracy is 79%. For the most studied classes, the accuracy is higher for the Landsat TM image (see Table 1 below).

Table 1. Level of accuracy

	Landsat MSS accuracy [%]	Landsat TM accuracy [%]
open mires	63	67
mire edge with some vegetation	59	70
drained mire/peat extraction	66	85
agricultural land	69	87
agricultural land not in use	58	82
urban areas	58	65
recent clear cut	80	80
Overall accuracy 79 %		

Annex C-4: Indicator Demonstration Broad Forest Habitat Inventory: Share of broadleaf/coniferous in a site (Test site “Kurgalsky peninsula”)

Definition

The indicator reports the area of a variety of forest types. Forest types described by dominant species of trees. Reduction of dominant species (stock reduction) testify to destruction of ecosystem and habitat state and habitat loss

By regularly examining it may be possible to detect deleterious changes and modify management strategies to reverse the change.

Geographical scope

Local, regional

Information needs /Questions that this indicator must answer

To provide information on changes in habitat and ecosystem and the cause of such change. Forest type may change as a result of direct human intervention (fire suppression, planting and harvesting, development, and grazing, air pollution and etc.) or because of natural succession. Changes in climate may also affect the range of different forest types. Forest area and forest type are foundational for most of the indicators

Project User Requirement

state of habitat/change in state of habitat. Distribution of forests species (forest type) by area.

Policy Relevance

Regional and National relevance to forest sustainable management

National biodiversity strategy and Action Plan (Ministry of Natural Resources, National biodiversity strategy and Action Plan. Moscow, Russia, 2001.

Russian Federation Forest Code, RF Federal Act No. 22-FZ. Adopted By The State Duma On January 22, 1997

Relevance to Habitat Directive

regional wildlife refuge, variety of anthropogenic impacts

1630 Boreal Baltic Coastal meadows

7310 mires

9020 natural old broad-leaved deciduous forest (Quercus)

Relevance to International Indicator framework

- Identify OECD Category State
- Structure/Function
- Identify criteria/indicator from the EEA core set indicator: Forestry, State
- MCPFE, Bear, ... CRITERION 1: Quantitative indicators: 1.1.

Intellectual source of the indicator

(1998) Annex 1 of the Resolution L2: Pan-European Criteria and Indicators for Sustainable Forest Management. Third Ministerial Conference on the Protection of Forests in Europe – Lisbon, Ministerial Conference on the Protection of Forests in Europe.

Environmental Indicators. Committee of environment protection of St Petersburg and Leningrad region (http://www.ecolog.nw.ru/LE_2.HTM)

Approach

In the classification of SAR images, texture provides important information in addition to image grey levels or the backscatter values alone. A large number of approaches for computation of image texture have been proposed and applied to SAR data to study land cover (e.g., Soares et al. 1994; Solberg et al. 1994; Renno and Freitas 1998; Kurvonen and Hallikainen 1999). In this study, the performance of texture features derived from the grey-level co-occurrence matrices (GLCM) is investigated. Two ERS-1 SAR images in PRI format were used to evaluate the performance of these texture features. The element of GLCM can be described as (Solberg et al. 1994):

$$P_{ij} = \frac{p_{ij}^{d,\alpha}}{\sum_{ij} p_{ij}^{d,\alpha}}, \quad (1)$$

where $p_{ij}^{d,\alpha}$ is the frequency of occurrence of grey levels i and j , separated by the distance d in the direction α , and L is the total number of pixel pairs within a window for given d and α values. The nature of the textural information contained in the GLCM depends on quantity of grey levels in the image (N), the size of the window (kernel), in which texture for a local area is computed, d and α .

In this study, the SAR images were quantised to 16 grey levels before computing the GLCM. A 9×9 -pixel kernel was chosen and the corresponding GLCM was assigned to the central pixel of this kernel. The value $d=1$ was used and for each kernel four GLCMs were calculated in directions of 0, 45, 90 and 135 degrees and then an average value was taken. Four textural features were selected for analysis, these are:

$$\text{Cluster Shade} = \sum_i \sum_j (i + j - \mu_i - \mu_j)^3 * P_{ij} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Contrast} = \sum_i \sum_j (i - j)^2 * P_{ij} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Entropy} = \sum_i \sum_j P_{ij} * \log P_{ij} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Inverse Moment} = \sum_i \sum_j \frac{1}{1 + (i - j)^2} * P_{ij} \quad (5)$$

where: $\mu_i = \sum_i i \sum_j P_{ij}$ $\mu_j = \sum_j j \sum_i P_{ij}$

Four textural maps were computed for each image, resulting in eight textural maps, which were then superimposed together with the two initial (i.e., not subjected to quantisation) images. The resulting ten-layer data set was subsequently classified using maximum likelihood supervised classification procedure. Four general types of forests were classified: coniferous, lowland coniferous, deciduous and mixed. Figure 1 presented methodological processing steps.

Fig.1 Methodological processing steps

Demonstration

The results of forest type classification are presented at Figure 2. Some similarity can be seen, especially for the coniferous forest stands. From Figure 2, it is also obvious that the resolution of the ground truth data map is much lower than that of the satellite-derived classification map. Table 1 presents the confusion matrix for the two maps given in Figure 2. The confusion matrix shows the correlation between retrieved and ground-truth data. The value at each cell of the matrix is the normalized count of the number of times that combination of the corresponding classes for these data occur. The confusion matrix shows that the best results were achieved for coniferous and mixed forests (52.2% and 44.3%). For lowland coniferous and deciduous forests, the accuracy of classification was lower (37.4% and 11.3%). However, the results are in agreement with the results obtained by other authors (Kurvonen and Hallikainen, 1999).

Figure 2. Results of forest type classification. To the left is the fragment of in-situ forest type map. To the right is the forest type classification map retrieved from satellite data. Four broad forest types are presented.

Table 1. Confusion Matrix for the Forest Type Classification from ERS/SAR data.

	Coniferous (%)	Lowland Coniferous (%)	Deciduous (%)	Mixed Forest (%)
Coniferous	52.2	23.3	29.1	24.2
Lowland Coniferous	27.7	34.7	30.6	21.1
Deciduous	3.7	8	11.3	10.4
MixedForest	16.4	34	29	44.3

The remote sensing-derived forest types classification maps provide substantially greater spatial detail than the contour maps based on ground-truth data. In itself, this illustrates an advantage of using remote sensing data; however, the relatively coarse resolution of the ground-truth maps precludes a comprehensive, spatially detailed error analysis. The accuracy of the classification of coniferous stands is not so high, but comparable to previous researchers.

Annex C-5: Indicator Demonstration Broad Forest Habitat Inventory: Share of broadleaf/coniferous in a site (Test site “Egorievsk”)

Definition:

This indicator shows the total area of the territory under forest and forest land and reports the area of a variety of forest types

Geographical scope

Local, regional

Information needs /Questions that this indicator must answer

To provide information on changes in habitat and ecosystem and the cause of such change. Forest type may change as a result of direct human intervention (fire suppression, planting and harvesting, development, and grazing, air pollution and etc.) or because of natural succession. Changes in climate may also affect the range of different forest types. Forest area and forest type are foundational for most of the indicators

Project User Requirement

state of habitat/change in state of habitat. Distribution of forests species (forest type) by area.

Policy Relevance

Regional and National relevance to forest sustainable management

National biodiversity strategy and Action Plan (Ministry of Natural Resources, National biodiversity strategy and Action Plan. Moscow, Russia, 2001.

Russian Federation Forest Code, RF Federal Act No. 22-FZ. Adopted By The State Duma On January 22, 1997

Indicators purpose:

Reporting and practical use for management at local and national level

Specific purpose: inventory and monitoring

Relevance to International Indicator framework:

OECD Category State (Structure/Function)

EEA indicator: Forestry, State

MCPFE, Bear: CRITERION 1: Quantitative indicators: 1.1.

Intellectual source of the indicator

(1998) Annex 1 of the Resolution L2: Pan-European Criteria and Indicators for Sustainable Forest Management. Third Ministerial Conference on the Protection of Forests in Europe – Lisbon, Ministerial Conference on the Protection of Forests in Europe.

Approach

The using of ground forest inventory data of test site from GIS database and SPOT XS satellite image has allowed us to carry out selection of sample plots (AOI) of different forest classes to assess its spectral signatures.

During selection of AOI, we have taken into account, and if it was possible minimized, the influence of the factors, that could reduce accuracy of spectral signature estimations. Among them is a residual error of co-registration of digital map and satellite image, heterogeneity in the atmosphere conditions, elimination of the mixed pixels on the transitions between land cover and forest types. To reduce an impact of these factors, we refined the standard samples by masking of their reflectance values into two-dimensional histogram of red and NIR spectral channel.

Within the study of spectral signatures, for each homogeneous group of land cover type we computed brightness average and standard deviation of each of the tree channels and values of Jeffries-Matusita (JM) distance. Last parameter allowed us to estimate separability of pairs of classes under analysis:

$JM_{ij} = \sqrt{2 \cdot (1 - e^{-\alpha})}$, where:

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{8}(\mu_i - \mu_j)^T \left(\frac{C_i - C_j}{2} \right)^{-1} (\mu_i - \mu_j) + \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{|(C_i + C_j)/2|}{\sqrt{|C_i| \times |C_j|}} \right), \quad (1)$$

i и j – signatures of pair of analyzing classes;

C_i – covariation matrix of the signature of i class;

μ_i - mean value of the signature of i class;

\ln – natural logarithm;

$|C_i|$ - determinant of C_i matrix

To investigate the spectral signatures, we have selected the samples of natural stands, representing following dominant species: pine, spruce, birch, aspen and black alder. The choice of the species was based not only on the test site statistics (more then 82% of the area of samples contains these tree species as dominant species) but also on the statistics of forest fund of the European part of Russia. Absolute values of stand ages were grouped into 5 classes using a standard scale of ages, adopted in Russia (table 1).

Table 1. Age class distribution of coniferous and deciduous forest stands

Forest stands	Minor and young	Young	Middle age	Premature	Mature and overmature
	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	Class 4	Class 5
Deciduous	Younger than 10 years	11 - 20	21 - 50	51 - 80	Older than 81
Coniferous	Younger than 20 years	21 - 40	41 - 90	91 - 140	Older than 140

The values of JM distance between pair classes for three spectral channels of SPOT image (B1, B2 and B3) are shown in the tables 2.

As a next step we analyzed values of Jeffries-Matusita distance between pairs of classes for each channel and compared them in order estimate the benefits of medium infrared band for classification of dominated specie stands of miscellaneous age.

Table 2 Values of normalized JM criteria for pair classes of dominated species and its ages with three channels (B1, B2 and B3 channels) of HRV image

Dominated specie and age classes	№	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Pine (1-st age)	1	0															
Pine (2-nd age)	2	44.6	0														
Pine (3-rd age)	3	59.3	34.0	0													
Pine (4-th age)	4	87.0	68.4	60.8	0												
Spruce(2-nd age)	5	57.4	27.9	33.0	64.9	0											
Spruce (3-rd age)	6	76.7	55.4	45.6	35.5	51.5	0										
Spruce (4-th age)	7	71.2	52.7	43.4	48.6	66.8	24.4	0									
Birch (1-st age)	8	52.1	49.0	46.4	80.4	45.6	66.3	54.1	0								
Birch (2-nd age)	9	62.2	61.7	59.2	83.4	55.0	72.2	58.3	34.4	0							
Birch (3-rd age)	10	67.6	60.0	55.3	82.0	45.6	70.7	56.2	36.0	29.0	0						
Birch (4-th age)	11	62.5	61.6	58.9	83.9	51.6	73.3	58.3	32.4	20.4	20.4	0					
Aspen (3-rd age)	12	81.1	73.5	58.7	79.1	57.9	72.4	63.8	57.1	57.1	45.2	45.9	0				
Aspen (4-th age)	13	82.5	80.3	65.5	87.9	69.9	80.8	71.2	55.1	54.4	49.8	45.7	25.0	0			
Alder(2-nd age)	14	62.3	79.8	87.7	96.6	85.3	92.6	90.3	77.8	83.6	87.9	82.7	94.2	94.2	0		
Alder(3-rd age)	15	64.5	78.7	80.6	94.1	79.9	88.6	81.9	64.6	61.4	73.3	63.5	81.0	75.7	71.0	0	
Alder(4-th age)	16	33.8	59.0	70.1	89.5	64.7	81.0	74.8	52.1	61.5	67.4	60.0	80.6	81.4	40.4	56.7	0

Fig.1 Methodological processing steps

Demonstration

Considering the data for ages types of each species, we have found out the correlation between the increments of JM value for coniferous stands (pine and spruce) and age distance between them. This tendency is seen for both data sets of HRVIR image, including and excluding MIR channel.

The absence of similar correlation for deciduous stands can be explained by changes in a foliage condition in the end of a vegetation season. It depends on the slowdown the processes of photosynthesis, change of foliage colour, and its falling down. It is resulted in the reduction of tree crowns density and, as a consequence, in an increase of the contribution of a grass and bare soil in spectral response of the deciduous forest cover.

SPOT XS

Fig.2 Forest type classification

The results of the classification here appear to be satisfactory. The value of divergence shows how well different forest classes can be separated on the SPOT image (see Table 1).

Table 1. Value of divergence for different forest classes

	young coniferous	middle coniferous	mature coniferous	young deciduous	middle deciduous	mature deciduous
young coniferous	0.00					
middle coniferous	0.80	0.00				
mature coniferous	0.99	0.70	0.00			
young deciduous	0.76	0.78	0.45	0.00		
middle deciduous	0.89	0.86	0.74	0.56	0.00	
mature deciduous	0.76	0.69	0.56	0.79	0.68	0.00

Based on the analysis of JM values for the forest stands with different dominated species from three spectral channels the following conclusions were made:

- Young stands of pine are well separated from spruce and aspen stands of older age classes;
- The class of premature pine is well separated from all age classes of deciduous species;
- The black alder stands of different ages are well separated from premature aspen;
- The values of JM criteria of the middle-aged alder demonstrate high separability from coniferous stands. The only exception is the class of young pine stands;

The considerable overlap of spectral brightness of all age classes of birch with other species is noted. That can be explained by the same reason of change of reflective properties of tree leaves during the end of vegetation season.

Annex C-6: Indicator Demonstration Broad Forest Habitat Inventory: Share of broadleaf/coniferous in a site (Test site “Flisa”)

Definition

The indicator reports the area of a variety of forest types. Forest types described by dominant species of trees. Reduction of dominant species (stock reduction) testify to destruction of ecosystem and habitat state and habitat loss

By regularly examining it may be possible to detect deleterious changes and modify management strategies to reverse the change.

Geographical scope

Local, regional

Information needs /Questions that this indicator must answer

To provide information on changes in habitat and ecosystem and the cause of such change. Forest type may change as a result of direct human intervention (fire suppression, planting and harvesting, development, and grazing, air pollution and etc.) or because of natural succession. Changes in climate may also affect the range of different forest types. Forest area and forest type are foundational for most of the indicators

Indicator purpose

Reporting and practical use for management at local level

Project User Requirement

state of habitat/change in state of habitat. Distribution of forests species (forest type) by area. Information on reduction of dominant species stock in percent to normal (optimal to current natural zone).

Policy Relevance

Regional and National relevance to forest sustainable management

Forestry and forest protection act (1993). (The objective of the Act is to promote forest production, forest protection and afforestation) (<http://english.dirnat.no/>)

The Planning and Construction Act, The Nature Protection Act and the Outdoor Recreation Act (all have an effect on the management of the forests in Norway) (<http://english.dirnat.no/>)

Nature Conservation Act (1970) (provisions for conservation of forests) (<http://english.dirnat.no/>)

Living forests Standards for Sustainable Forest Management in Norway (<http://www.levendeskog.no>)

Relevance to Habitat Directive

Habitat state

9010 * Western Taïga

(anemone hepatica, conitum septen-trionale)

Relevance to International Indicator framework

- OECD Category -State

- Structure/Function

- EEA core set EEA indicator: Forestry, State
- MCPFE, Bear, ... CRITERION 1: Quantitative indicators: 1.1.

Intellectual source of the indicator

(2001) Indicators and Environmental Impact Assessment: Designing national-level monitoring and indicator programs. UNEP/CBD/SBSTTA/7/12 – Montreal, Subsidiary Body on Scientific, Technical and Technological Advice

Living forests Standards for Sustainable Forest Management in Norway (<http://www.levendeskog.no>)

Approach

An unsupervised classification of Landsat MSS and TM 1985/1999 scenes has been performed for the Glomma (Flisa) areas. The rectification of the Landsat MSS scenes is based on digital and conventional maps in addition to rectification points from field. During processing of the Landsat TM image, we used 4 bands corresponding with Landsat MSS. Based on our and other researchers' experience we found out that the results do not much depend on the difference in resolution. So, we worked with original resolution of both images.

Classifications with 16, 40 and 80 classes were identified to characterise the land cover. The interpretation of the classified images was primary based on ground-truth data from fieldwork. The interpretation and classification of the images is a process continuously revised by the ground truth data from fieldwork.

The selection of training sites is based so far on the unsupervised classification of the Landsat MSS scenes with 16 classes as well as on fieldwork in the Glomma study area. All these classes have been checked; however they still need revisions and collection on in situ data particularly in agricultural and human made areas.

The 16 classes of land cover in the unsupervised classification of Landsat MSS scenes for the Flisa areas represents water, water mixed with stone/grass (bridges, shores of lakes), pine, spruce, mixed forest, deciduous forest, marsh, human made area, different classes of cultivation land (shifting cultivation, pastures, grass), snow, and clouds.

The change detection approach includes the "post-classification comparison" and "image difference" methods.

Fig. 1 Multi-temporal remote sensing data for forest type classification and change detection

Demonstration

Supervised classifications of the 1985 MSS and 1999 TM data are made in several steps. The same reference data as used for the 1999 classification are used in classification of MSS data. However, classes subject to changes, e.g. clearcut and young forest, are revised for each dataset. Nevertheless, the lower resolution of MSS data makes it difficult to distinguish classes that are easier to distinguish in the TM image: e.g. non-forested bogs and clearcuts, and young forest and forested bogs. Because the main use of MSS images is for a time-series analysis where the output should be age of forest stands, a forest mask is made from the TM image and a new set of raster maps where only these areas of the MSS images are classified are produced.

At the diagrams at figure 1 is shown the change of the areas of dominant forest type.

- | | |
|---------------------------------|-----------------------------------|
| 1. open mires | 2. mire edge with some vegetation |
| 3. drained mire/peat extraction | 4. deciduous forest |
| 5. spruce | 6. pine |
| 7. mixed pine and deciduous | |

Fig. 2 Diagram shows the change of the areas of dominant forest type (difference between 1985 and 1999)

The level of accuracy is encouraging – the overall accuracy is 79%. For the most studied classes, the accuracy is higher for the Landsat TM image (see Table 1).

Table 1 Level of accuracy for studied classes.

	Landsat MSS accuracy [%]	Landsat TM accuracy [%]
open mires	63	67
mire edge with some vegetation	59	70
drained mire/peat extraction	66	85
deciduous forest	77	75
spruce	62	85
pine	60	73
mixed pine and deciduous	55	59
Overall accuracy 79 %		

Annex C-7: Indicator Demonstration Broad Forest Habitat state: area and proportion of coniferous species damaged by air pollution (Test site “Kurgalsky peninsula”)

Definition

Main coniferous species are especially sensitive to air pollution. Degree of crown defoliation in the stands is an indicator that characterizes the forest condition.

Geographical scope

Local, regional

Information needs/Question that this indicator must answer

To provide the information of forest condition and degree of anthropogenic pressure. When health and structure of forest ecosystems are getting worsens then biodiversity and productivity decreases, and destructive processes is accelerate in this polluted environment

Indicator purpose

Reporting and practical use for management at local level

Project User Requirement

habitat state /change in state of habitat

Policy Relevance

Convention on Long-Range Transboundary of Air Pollution International Co-operative Programme on Assessment and Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Forest

BALTIC 21:An Agenda 21 for the Baltic Sea Region (The Agenda 21 for the Baltic Sea Region -- Baltic 21-- was adopted by the Foreign Ministers at the meeting of the Council of the Baltic Sea States on 22-23 June, 1998 (Nyborg, Denmark) (<http://www.ee/baltic21/>))

Relevance to Habitat Directive

regional wildlife refuge, variety of anthropogenic impacts

Habitats/Species of European Interest relevant to the indicator

1630 Boreal Baltic Coastal meadows

7310 mires

9020 natural old broad-leaved deciduous forest (Quercus)

Relevance to International Indicator framework

- OECD Category-) State

- Structure/Function

- *criteria/indicator from the EEA core set* EEA indicator: Forestry, State

- *MCPFE, Bear, ...* CRITERION 2: Quantitative indicators: 2.1. 2.2.

Intellectual source of the indicator

UN/ECE, 2001. Forest condition in Europe. Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution International Co-operative Programme on Assessment and Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Forest and European Union Scheme on the Protection of Forests against Atmospheric pollution. UN/ECE and EC, Geneva and Brussels, 2001

UN/ECE, 1992, Forest Condition in Europe. International Co- operative Program on Assessment and Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Forests. Brussels, Geneva, 117 pp.

Environmental Indicators .Committee of environment protection of St Petersburg and Leningrad region (http://www.ecolog.nw.ru/LE_2.HTM)

Approach

These *in situ* data on the intensity of forest damage were acquired from mid July to the end of August. Morphological indicators of the trees were taken as the basic criteria of the forest status. In most cases, to assess the degree of damage, phenological data and the visual inspection indicators of the state of the trees are preferred (Donchenko, 1998). The mere crown appearance, especially in the case of coniferous trees, reflects the response of plants to their sliding into an unfavourable ecological niche. (Goltsova, 1992 and 1995). The development of the degenerative process in pine needles leads to a decrease of the velocity of respiration and photosynthesis, slowing down the rate of chlorophyll synthesis (Goltsova and Vasina, 1995, Guderian, 1979). This is reflected on the tree's external indicators resulting in colour change and death of pine needles – this change can be imaged from for example Landsat MSS. Changes in the trees appearance (measured in % of colour degradation of pine needles or/and degree of defoliation) are important factors in the visual assessment of the state of crowns.

Fig. 1 Forest state assessment algorithm

Demonstration

Comparison of NDVI of RESURS-01 MSU-SK with the *in situ* data represents the spatial distribution of the mercury (Hg) in the forest moss over the test site. Since the content of Hg in the forest moss is in direct proportion its S content, the damaged forest areas could be easily identified by a high concentration of Hg in the forest moss

Fig.2 Landsat/MSS NDVI map (to the left) and the in-situ data presenting distribution of pine needles discoloration (to the right).

This figure 2 shows the presence of the correspondence between the healthy tree areas on the satellite-derived map and the areas of low degree of pine needle discoloration on the ground truth map (high values of NDVI correspond with healthy trees, low values – stressed trees). The area below Narva Reservoir, around Slantsy quarry, has very low NDVI values – on the ground truth map, this area corresponds to the highest degree of pine needle discoloration. The high values of NDVI, in the bottom – right part of the remote sensing derived map, correspond well with the low discoloration values in this region on ground truth map. Additionally relevant connections and relationships between the parameters obtained by multi-spectral satellite sensors, such as NDVI, and the factors inducing plant stress were established.

These results can be used to produce maps indicating the degree of forest degradation and for estimating the area of damaged and healthy forests. For example, the state of the forest in the study area was assessed on the basis of the NDVI distribution as derived from multi-spectral satellite surveys. For the reliably identified forests, a distinction was made between healthy trees (i.e., having high NDVI values) and trees weakened by air pollution. It was found that about 1050 km² of forested areas in the Kingisepp district and 600 km² in the Slantsy district have the vegetation index values below the normal level (about 25% of the total forested area).

The correlation is encouraging. It is apparent from the correlation analysis that a range of parameter defining the degree of forest degradation has strong dependencies with optical remote sensing data. But still the ground truth data is closer to the truth than the NDVI map. Nevertheless optical data have the potential for identifying areas of damaged forest, at least where some *in situ* data are available for validation.

Annex C-8: Indicator Demonstration Broad Forest Habitat state: forest under threat due to air pollution effect (Test site “Kurgalsky peninsula”)

Definition

The degree and spatial distribution of ecological anomalies in forests that appear under the influence of air pollution

Geographical scope

Local, regional

Information needs /Questions that this indicator must answer

To provide the information of forest condition and degree of anthropogenic pressure. When health and structure of forest ecosystems are getting worsens then biodiversity and productivity decreases, and destructive processes is accelerate in this polluted environment

Indicator purpose

Reporting and practical use for management at local level

Project User Requirement

habitat state /change in state of habitat

Policy Relevance

Convention on Long-Range Transboundary of Air Pollution International Co-operative Programme on Assessment and Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Forest

BALTIC 21:An Agenda 21 for the Baltic Sea Region (The Agenda 21 for the Baltic Sea Region -- Baltic 21-- was adopted by the Foreign Ministers at the meeting of the Council of the Baltic Sea States on 22-23 June, 1998 (Nyborg, Denmark) (<http://www.ee/baltic21/>))

Relevance to Habitat Directive

regional wildlife refuge, variety of anthropogenic impacts

Habitats/Species of European Interest relevant to the indicator

1630 Boreal Baltic Coastal meadows

7310 mires

9020 natural old broad-leaved deciduous forest (Quercus)

Relevance to International Indicator framework

- OECD Category-) State
- Structure/Function
- *criteria/indicator from the EEA core set* EEA indicator: Forestry, State
- *MCPFE, Bear, ...* CRITERION 2: Quantitative indicators: 2.1. 2.2.

Intellectual source of the indicator

UN/ECE, 2001. Forest condition in Europe. Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution International Co-operative Programme on Assessment and Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Forest and European Union Scheme on the Protection of Forests against Atmospheric pollution. UN/ECE and EC, Geneva and Brussels, 2001

UN/ECE, 1992, Forest Condition in Europe. International Co-operative Program on Assessment and Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Forests. Brussels, Geneva, 117 pp.

Environmental Indicators .Committee of environment protection of St Petersburg and Leningrad region (http://www.ecolog.nw.ru/LE_2.HTM)

Approach

The accuracy of the estimates of industrially damaged forest depends much on the accuracy of contouring forested areas. This is due to the fact that changes in spectral characteristics of the surface caused by natural and industrial impacts on the vegetation depend not only upon the impact strength but also on the type of the surface (Donchenko et al. 1997, 2000). Moreover, for this study, it is important to know if the degradation of vegetation is induced by industrial pollution or by natural conditions. Therefore, the targets should be thoroughly selected, especially within the areas with decreased spectral indices. It is these areas, which include the sites of industrially damaged forest that were finally chosen for monitoring.

Fig. 1 Forest state assessment algorithm

Demonstration

Figure 2 presents the comparison of the forest state map derived from spatial distribution of RESURS-01 MSU-SK NDVI with the ground truth data showing the level of Hg pollution over the test site. This figure shows that the areas having a high level of Hg in forest moss on the ground truth map generally correspond well to the areas of unhealthy trees on the NDVI-derived map.

The strip of the low NDVI values, which stretches from the bottom-right to the upper-left corner of the remote sensing-derived map, is also present on the ground truth map of Hg deposits distribution as the region of high level of Hg pollution. And the area of high value of NDVI in the upper-right part of satellite map corresponds well with the area of low values of Hg pollution on the ground truth map.

Fig.2 RESURS-01 MSU-SK NDVI derived forest state map (to the left) and in-situ data presenting mercury deposits distribution in forest moss over the test site (to the right). The red curve on the RESURS-01 map outlines Narva Reservoir. On the left image the zones coloured in blue presenting damaged forest coincide with the zones coloured in deep blue on the right image presenting higher concentrations of mercury.

Again, the correlation is encouraging. But still the ground truth data is closer to the truth than the NDVI map.